

Review

Fitness for transport assessment for end-of-lay hens

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1 Executive Summary

Transportation, together with catching and crating, can be extremely stressful procedures. Hence, planning and correctly assessing the fitness of the birds to withstand the journey are essential to maintain an adequate level of welfare during transportation. End-of-lay hens are at particular risk of experiencing negative welfare consequences during catching and transportation due to their compromised physiological state (weakened bones, metabolic exhaustion and poor feather cover) and long travel distances to the few slaughterhouses available for the slaughtering of this type of birds. Before loading, inspectors and personnel need to know which fitness characteristics to inspect in order to determine whether the birds are fit or not to cope with the transport challenges (e.g. fasting, trailer movements, noise, vibrations, social disruption or thermal stress). However, European regulations do not define the terms “fit” or “unfit” for transport and there are no reviews nor guidelines that discuss the relevancy and assessment methods for on-farm indicators to assess the fitness for transport for end-of-lay hens. The present document discusses the definition of fitness for transport and reviews the animal-based indicators to be considered for the assessment of fitness for transport of end-of-lay hens, based on the literature and opinion of the authors. The selected indicators are: presence of severe open wounds, prolapses, severe lameness, broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations, keel bone damage, emaciation and cachexia, dehydration, poor feather cover, wet plumage and evident signs of illness. For each indicator, a brief definition, the methods available for their assessment, the criteria used to decide the fitness for transport of birds and the knowledge gaps encountered are included. It has been found that clear and specific definitions for laying hens are missing for some of the indicators selected, as the terms used are general, have been established for other species, or are imprecise. Regarding the methods available, although some of the selected indicators have multiple scoring methods validated for laying hens on farm, there is no scoring method for assessing them in terms of fitness for transport. In other cases, there are no specific methods developed for laying hens at all. Even if assessment methods are available, in some cases there is a lack of thresholds to differentiate whether the animals are fit or unfit for the journey. Finally, some of the existing methods for the assessment of certain indicators rely on palpation or visual inspection, meaning that handling of the animals is needed. This can be time consuming, and an assessment strategy should be discussed. In conclusion, a substantial quantity of gaps of knowledge have been found. They should be addressed before practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of end-of-lay hens can be produced.

2 Abbreviations

ABI or ABIs	Abbreviation of "Animal Based Indicator/s"
AET	Abbreviation of "Apparent equivalent temperature"
CA or CAs	Abbreviation of "Competent Authority/ies"
DoA	Abbreviation of "Dead/s on Arrival"
EoL	Abbreviation of "End-of-lay"
FFT	Abbreviation of "Fitness for transport"
KBF	Abbreviation of "Keel bone fracture"
KBD	Abbreviation of "Keel bone deviation"

3 Introduction

Transportation is an essential step in the meat industry, but it can be extremely stressful for poultry, even leading up to death (Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017; Schwartzkopf-Genswein et al., 2012). Transport might expose birds to a range of hazards such as a new environment with reduced space allowance, temperature changes, excessive or inadequate ventilation, water and food withdrawal, vibrations, and noise. These hazards impair their welfare and the longer the journey duration the longer the exposure to the hazards, and greater the severity of the welfare consequences such as pain, thermal stress, prolonged hunger or restricted movement (EFSA et al., 2022; Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017). Moreover, these negative welfare consequences during transport are greater for animals which are injured or sick, increasing the chance to die during the journey because they are less able to cope with the different hazards that might apply (EFSA et al., 2022; Herskin et al., 2021).

Making sure that animals are fit to withstand the journey to the final destination is of utmost importance (Cockram, 2019; Grandin, 2001). Animals shall be checked, before loading, to determine their fitness for transport (FFT) in order to maintain an adequate level of welfare during transportation. Unfit animals should be euthanized if required (European Parliament: Directorate-General for Parliamentary Research Services et al., 2018). Therefore, inspectors and other professionals involved (farmers, veterinarians, livestock drivers) need to know which fitness characteristics to inspect (Herskin et al., 2021). Thresholds to differentiate between fit and unfit birds must be carefully considered, as they may have a large impact upon economic losses (Jacobs et al., 2017). Legal requirements regarding FFT will be discussed in [section 4](#), but European regulations do not define the term “fit” nor “unfit”. Extensive research on the impacts of transportation of meat birds have been done, but it seems there is no universally accepted scientific definition of the expression “fitness for transport”. Some guidelines address the topic of poultry transport (*Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual*, 2019; Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; European poultry transport guide, 2016; Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017). However, the FFT topic represents a small part of their content, as they focus on improving planning of the journey, handling, means of transport, etc. The LEGMONI project has focused in easy-to-use ABIs for end-of-lay (EoL) hens, but at the slaughterhouse, as it is a tool intended for monitoring welfare (LEGMONI Project et al., 2024), but some research for improving the selection, catching and loading of broilers was also made by the same authors (KIPVANG Project et al., 2023). Some countries have internal guidelines for the assessment of FFT in poultry (e.g. Denmark, Wales), but they do not include all the possible indicators in detail. To the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA knowledge, there are no reviews nor guidelines that discuss the relevancy and assessment methods for on-farm indicators to assess FFT.

FFT of EoL hens is specially concerning due to hens’ particular physiological characteristics and journey conditions (which will be presented in detail in [sections 5, 6 and 7](#)). Although transportation makes up a small percentage of an individual hen’s lifespan (which are usually sent to slaughter after 52-100 weeks of life)(EFSA et al., 2022), it has a high potential for causing severe negative welfare consequences to the birds during this period.

The EURCAW-Poultry-SFA decided to first approach the topic of FFT in EoL hens in a workshop held during the 2022 meeting between the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA and Competent Authorities (CAs). Then, in 2023 the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA sent a questionnaire to the CAs in order to gather more information about the current practices regarding transport of EoL hens. Finally, this information was presented and discussed during another workshop held online in 2023. The EURCAW-Poultry-SFA concluded that FFT was a topic of great interest for the CAs, who lacked guidance about Animal Based Indicators (ABIs) and visual material to assess them properly, especially for EoL hens.

Therefore, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA will present in the present document a comprehensive overview of the EoL hens' particular situation. European legislation will be presented and the definition of FFT will be discussed. A brief section about inspections will also be presented. Candidate indicators to consider laying hens unfit for transport will be discussed and a final list of selected indicators to review will be presented, as well as the methodology used for review. Then, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA will review in detail the selected indicators for FFT, including a brief definition, the available methodologies for their assessment, criteria used for deciding the birds' FFT, and the gaps of knowledge encountered.

The present document mainly refers to EoL hens (*Gallus gallus*) in all breeds, but it may also apply to other types of hens like broiler breeders or layer breeders. However, the reader should be aware that, if similar principles remain applicable, some adaptation may be necessary due to the specific characteristics of each type of bird.

4 European legislation, definition of fitness for transport and official inspections

Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005 of 22 December 2004, on the protection of animals during transport, requires that fitness for transport should be assessed before starting the transport and animals unfit for transport should not be transported. In order to protect animals during transport, they have to be fit when the journey starts (Cockram, 2019; Grandin, 2001).

Fitness for transport also appears in the *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/624 of 8 February 2019*, concerning specific rules for the performance of official controls on the production of meat and for production and relaying areas of live bivalve molluscs in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council:

«(c) Ante-mortem inspections at the holding of provenance shall comprise a physical examination of the animals to determine whether: (...) (v) they are **fit for transport**» (Article 5, point 2).

Although these regulations do not clearly define the term "fit" or "unfit", *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005* describe conditions that **should not happen**:

«No animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey, and all animals shall be transported in conditions guaranteed not to cause them **injury** or **unnecessary suffering**» (Annex I, Chapter I, Point 1).

«Animals that are **injured** or that present **physiological weaknesses** or **pathological processes** shall not be considered fit for transport and in particular if:

- (a) they are **unable to move** independently without pain or to walk unassisted;
- (b) they present a **severe open wound**, or **prolapse**;

However, sick or injured animals may be considered fit for transport if they are:

- (a) slightly injured or ill and transport would not cause additional suffering; in cases of doubt, veterinary advice shall be sought» (Annex I, Chapter I, Point 2).

The lack of a legal definition of “fitness” is a challenge for the development and validation of indicators of FFT to be used during inspections, as the term “fitness” can have different interpretations. Additionally, animals which are going to be rejected as unfit for human consumption could not be transported to the slaughterhouse to avoid exposing them unnecessarily to transportation. Moreover, the assessment is also complicated because the regulation states that animals should be fit for “the intended journey”, so professionals need to take into account the planned journeys.

Official inspections

There are several persons involved in the assessment of FFT. *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005 of 22 December 2004* states that the keeper and the driver have responsibilities regarding FFT:

«No person shall transport animals or cause animals to be transported in a way likely to cause injury or undue suffering to them. (...) the following conditions shall be complied with (...) the animals are **fit for the journey**» (Article 3, letter b).

«Transporters shall transport animals in accordance with the technical rules set out in **Annex I**» (Article 6, point 3).

«Keepers of animals at the place of departure, transfer or destination shall ensure that the technical rules set out in Chapters I and III, section 1, of **Annex I** in respect of the animals being transported are met» (Article 8, point 1).

The involvement of the farm personnel in the assessment of FFT during the routine checks is key to ensure that unfit birds are found and removed beforehand (Jacobs et al., 2017), especially in large houses. Protocols for early identification of animals that need to be culled or treated are recommended, as part of the farm welfare plans (Cockram, 2019). Farm veterinarians should encourage them and provide advice and training on the topic (Cockram, 2019; Doonan et al.,

2014). The farmer, or a nominated representative, should also supervise the catching and loading to detect fitness problems due to handling (Poultry Service Association et al., 2017). Unfit animals detected during catching should not be loaded, and the catching crew should be instructed on how to deal with them (Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017).

Official inspections must also take place, usually at farm, according to *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/624 of 8 February 2019*:

«By way of derogation from Article 18(2)(a) and (b) of Regulation (EU) 2017/625, the competent authority may allow **ante-mortem inspections** on animals intended for slaughter to be **performed at the holding of provenance**» (Article 5, point 1).

«The following criteria and conditions shall be applied for all species: (...)

(c) ante-mortem inspections at the holding of provenance shall comprise a physical examination of the animals to determine whether: (...) (v) they are **fit for transport**.

(d) The checks and ante-mortem inspection at the holding of provenance (...) shall be carried out by an **official veterinarian**» (Article 5, point 2).

However, the ante-mortem inspections can be delegated, according to *Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017*, on official controls:

«Competent authorities **may delegate** certain official control tasks to one or more delegated bodies or natural persons in accordance with the conditions provided for in Articles 29 and 30 respectively. The competent authority shall ensure that the delegated body or natural person, to which such tasks have been delegated, have the powers needed to effectively perform these tasks» (Article 28, points 1 and 2).

For this reason, FFT assessment in farm is usually performed by authorised farm veterinarians (who also issue the health certificate for the journey), and not by official veterinary inspectors. The state of the animals is checked again at the slaughterhouse as part of the ante-mortem inspections for food safety purposes by the slaughterhouse official veterinary inspectors, as stated in *Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing*:

«The **welfare conditions** of each consignment of animals shall be systematically assessed by the animal welfare officer or a person reporting directly to the animal welfare officer **upon arrival** in order to identify the priorities, in particular by determining which animals have specific welfare needs and the corresponding measures to be taken» (Annex III, point 1.1)

In the case of long journeys, an official control is mandatory according to *Regulation (EU) 2017/625*:

«Official controls to verify compliance with the rules laying down welfare requirements for animals in the event of their transport, in particular with Regulation (EC) No 1/2005, shall include:

(a) in the case of long journeys between Member States and with third countries, **official controls** performed prior to the loading to check the **fitness of the animals for transport**; (...)

(c) at border control posts provided for in Article 59(1) and at exit points:(i) **official controls on the fitness of the animals being transported** and on the means of transport to verify compliance with Chapter II of **Annex I** to Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 and where applicable Chapter VI thereof; (...)» (Article 21, point 2).

Therefore, farmers, livestock drivers, veterinarians and inspectors all play a role in ensuring that EoL hens are fit for transport. However, it is beyond the scope of this review to include how tasks and responsibilities should be distributed between these professional groups.

Inspection conditions

A final inspection of FFT should be done within 12 hours prior to catching (as close as possible to the time of catching), in order to minimise the risk of animals becoming unfit in the meantime, and because of the difficulties to observe some of the FFT conditions during the catching and loading phase (e.g. lameness or illness) (EFSA et al., 2022). Nonetheless, birds must also be inspected during catching and crating, and any unfit animal detected should be separated for treatment or culling.

Suitable working conditions are key to identifying unfit animals (e.g. ensuring proper light). The evaluation method should also be quick and practical. Large houses may not allow to see all the animals at once. In this case, several transects within the house are recommended i.e. visual observation of birds while slowly walking through the barn along longitudinal predetermined bands (transects) of equal width according to the house width (see "[Iceberg indicator factsheet: severe feather pecking](#)") (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2022b) for an example of transect method in laying hens).

Monitoring at the slaughterhouse

Some conditions are difficult to detect ante-mortem (e.g. ascites), or easier to detect after removal of feathers (e.g. injuries). Monitoring condemnation causes and post-mortem injuries on the carcasses at slaughter can provide information about on-farm welfare, transport welfare and

pre-slaughter handling (Saraiva et al., 2021; Valkova et al., 2021). The collection of this data for welfare monitoring could contribute to control and improve animal health and welfare (Vecerek et al., 2019). However, it would be useful to adapt condemnation codes for EoL hens situation in order to improve the recording of condemnation causes accuracy (Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Moe, et al., 2023).

5 End-of-lay hens' special situation: physiology

Council Regulation (EC 1/2005) has as central requirement which states that animals presenting signs of **pathological processes** or **physiological weakness** shall not be considered fit for transport. It should be acknowledged that EoL hens, being at the end of the production cycle, might be:

- Metabolically exhausted with few body reserves, so there is a higher risk of prolonged hunger after feed withdrawal of 10 hours (EFSA et al., 2022);
- Still laying eggs of high-water content, so there is a higher risk of prolonged thirst after 12 hours of water deprivation (EFSA et al., 2022);
- Poorly feathered owing to wear and tear feather loss in cage systems and to injurious pecking in all systems, so they may be more sensitive to cold stress (EFSA et al., 2022);
- Birds with weak bones or osteoporosis (EFSA et al., 2022). Osteoporosis is a pathological condition, which is associated with progressive loss of structural bone throughout lay, thereby rendering bones fragile and susceptible to fracture (EFSA et al., 2022; FAWC, 2010).

Thus, EoL hens are at particular risk of experiencing negative welfare consequences during catching (e.g. bone fractures) and during transport, and FFT should be assessed thoroughly. They may be less able to cope with the challenges occurring during transport, especially if they have a painful condition that could worsen during the journey. Animals sent for slaughter with pre-existing conditions are more likely to die in transit or be condemned as unfit for human consumption upon arrival at the slaughterhouse (Cockram, 2019; Lambooi, 2014). For this reason, and for the reduced economic value of EoL hens' carcasses, sometimes it is decided to kill the animals on-farm and send them to rendering instead of transporting them to the slaughterhouse. However, this is not the main situation in the European Union, where most EoL hens are killed in slaughterhouses (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA questionnaire, 2023).

6 End-of-lay hens' special situation: catching and crating

Catching and crating are stressful procedures, whose severity will depend on the birds' genetics, the familiarity with people and the quality of handling (Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022). When birds are caught and carried in an inverted position, handling stress and risk of injuries (dislocated joints, fractures in legs or wings and bruises) are increased (EFSA et al., 2022). The results of Kittelsen et al. (2018) showed that the abdominal and upright method was also associated to less placement of broilers on their back in the drawers

and less Deaths on Arrival (DoA). Moreover, catching and crating of EoL hens represents a particularly high risk of injuries, for the reasons explained above (EFSA et al., 2022) and their low economic value, which does not encourage a careful handling either (Petracci et al., 2006).

EoL hens can be caught from cages or aviaries. In cages, access to the animals can be difficult, and there is a risk that the animals may be struck against structures (EFSA et al., 2022; Weeks et al., 2019). Besides, handling is especially important: the removal of EoL hens from cages by holding the birds by two legs compared with a single leg reduced the amount of fractures from about 13% to 5% (Gregory et al., 1992 as cited in EFSA et al., 2022). In aviaries, furniture structure (e.g. perches and nest boxes) sometimes makes the catching more difficult, and birds can escape easily from the catching crew (FAWC, 2019). EoL hens tend to crowd and pile up at the end of aisles, which might also cause smothering or attempts to flap and fly (EFSA et al., 2022). Whichever the housing system is used, EoL hens can also be injured when introduced into the transport crates, depending on the size of the crate openings and handling.

As said before, EoL hens usually have weak bones or osteoporosis (FAWC, 2010). The study of Gerpe et al. (2021) found that 8.1% of hens sustained fractures and severe muscle damage on catching and crating of hens housed in aviaries in Switzerland. A survey in UK carried out by Sandilands et al. (2005) found that 26-55% of laying hens had sustained fractures during production and 4-25% during depopulation, depending on the housing system (Weeks et al., 2019). The occurrences of keel-bone damage, hyperkeratosis and missing toes are also greater in older hens (Riber & Hinrichsen, 2016). Moreover, Gerpe et al. (2021) discussed that weak bones of EoL hens are prone to break as a result of rough handling, because bones may fracture even in the absence of collisions (or, at least, as a result of collisions with low energy impact). In the specific case of sternum fractures, they may result from the excessive force of the muscles involved in wing flapping (independently of contact with the furniture)(Gerpe et al., 2021).

For these reasons, a fit hen can easily become unfit during catching and crating procedures. In that case, the bird should be identified, separated and euthanized.

7 End-of-lay hens' special situation: transportation

Planning is essential to identify potential welfare consequences and possible hazards during transport, so preventive and mitigation measures can be implemented (e.g. estimation of the transport duration, analysis of weather forecast, correct communication within the catching crew, drivers and slaughterhouse staff)(Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022).

EoL hens are not accepted in all commercial slaughterhouses (generally only in 1 to 3 per Member State (EFSA et al., 2022)), as they have low economic value and entail some technical difficulties (adaptation of the slaughter equipment)(European Commission, 2023). As a result, EoL hens are often transported for longer distances than other poultry, hence they are exposed longer to the

transport conditions (Çavuşoğlu & Petek, 2021; EFSA et al., 2022; European Commission, 2023; Faucitano, 2022; Vecerkova et al., 2019). Furthermore, the majority of EoL hens are killed on slaughterhouses, not on farm (EFSA et al., 2022; Vecerkova et al., 2019). This was confirmed by the results of the questionnaire sent by the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA in 2023 to the Member States, which also showed that the average travel distance of hens from farm to slaughter within a country is 150-300 km, and 100-800 km when transported to another country (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA questionnaire, 2023). The information gathered in the questionnaire was not sufficient to provide an exhaustive overview of current practices, but it helped to identify the magnitude of the situation: that is, the assessment of FFT on-farm for EoL hens is essential because most of them will be transported for slaughter, either short or long distances.

For EoL hens, there are two highlighted welfare consequences regarding transportation: long-distance transports that can lead to prolonged hunger and thirst, and weather conditions that can lead to cold stress or heat stress.

Long-distance transport: prolonged hunger and thirst

Birds transported in containers are usually deprived of feed before being caught and crated for hygiene, practical and economic reasons (EFSA et al., 2022). This practice can lead to prolonged hunger in all birds, as it can happen from a few hours to even several days (EFSA et al., 2022). Additionally, producers may sometimes reduce the quantity or quality of feed as hens approach the end of lay (EFSA et al., 2023). Birds are also water deprived during transport (but seldom before catching), which can lead to prolonged thirst and dehydration.

In addition to the particular conditions presented above ([section 5](#)), EoL hens usually have a period of 8 hours at night without feed, so when they are caught at night they may have a full crop with food reserves to sustain them during transport (EFSA et al., 2022). But in large cage housing, only part of the flock may be removed in one day, and if feed is not distributed to the remaining animals, the feed withdrawal period could be longer. They could also suffer longer lairage time if transport is not well planned and they have to be slaughtered at the end of the working day (i.e. for hygienic reasons if the same plant slaughters broilers and hens).

EFSA et al. (2022) concluded that in the thermal comfort zone, EoL hens will experience prolonged hunger after feed withdrawal from at least 10 hours (and maybe earlier, but there is no scientific data of the effect of less than 10 hours of feed deprivation), instead of the 12 hours of feed withdrawal stated by broilers and turkeys. EFSA et al. (2022) also concluded that EoL hens subjected to water deprivation periods longer than 6 hours will experience prolonged thirst (the same as in broilers, but with an increased risk because hens are still producing eggs), that will increase with time. The total time of water deprivation should not exceed 12 hours in the safe thermo-neutral zone.

Weather conditions: cold stress or heat stress

Thermal stress, either prolonged heat or cold stress, has detrimental effects (stress, discomfort or distress) on poultry welfare during transportation (Çavuşoğlu & Petek, 2021). It can be experienced for the entire journey or for parts of it, and severity will increase over time, until birds will eventually fail to cope with it and die (EFSA et al., 2022). The number of birds loaded per

crate should be adapted according to the bird state and the weather, lairage time, and environmental conditions (Çavuşoğlu & Petek, 2021).

Heat stress is less common than cold stress in EoL hens, but it's relevant in hot weather conditions. In poultry, most of the heat loss under hot conditions occurs through panting, as they lack sweat glands, and its efficiency depends on the level of humidity in the air. Moreover, painting is a temporary solution: if it is prolonged there is a high risk of birds experiencing prolonged thirst and dehydration (EFSA et al., 2022).

EFSA et al. (2022) suggested a thermoneutral limit for EoL hens at 28°C and 60% relative humidity and recommended the same ranges of temperature and humidity suggested for broilers in the apparent equivalent temperature (AET) index (Figure 1). Birds should travel in the "safe zone" corresponding to AET values below 40 in order to prevent heat stress. However, they could be transported when they are in the "alert zone" for journey durations up to 4 hours.

Figure 1. Thermal Comfort Zones for broiler transport defined by apparent equivalent temperature (source: EFSA et al. (2022))

EoL hens are often poorly feathered, which is not a problem for higher temperatures, but for cold stress (lack of insulation makes them more sensitive to cold) (EFSA et al., 2022). Therefore, combined with the fact that they lack fat cover and musculature to keep them warm by shivering, the risk of experiencing cold stress is greater in EoL hens than in other poultry, and it has been associated to increased DoA (EFSA et al., 2022). Besides, the stress during production related to feather damage makes the animals less able to cope with transport stressors (EFSA et al., 2022).

Furthermore, wetting and air movement have a significant impact on insulation and should be avoided because it leads to hypothermia even with mild temperatures that would only have represented a small decrease in body temperature if birds had been kept dry (EFSA et al., 2022).

EFSA et al. (2022) suggested that temperature should be maintained above 18°C regardless of the feather cover, instead of the 10 °C recommended for broilers.

Panting is a practical indicator for assessing heat stress in birds during transport, as shivering is for cold stress, but they both concern environmental conditions and not the birds' fitness for transport. However, some indicators that will be later described in this review are specifically linked to cold stress (i.e. wet animals and poor feather cover), given the importance of this hazard. If a high proportion of animals is panting or shivering, and the weather and transport conditions are not suitable to counteract the heat or cold stress, transport should be delayed until better conditions could be assured.

8 Candidate indicators to consider laying hens unfit for transport

In the "Fitness for transport of pigs" report from EURCAW-Pigs (Herskin et al., 2021), the concepts of "injury" and "unnecessary suffering" stated in the Regulation are examined, and the possibilities to use these terms as the basis for the development of indicators of FFT are discussed. That discussion also applies to poultry and will not be reproduced in this report again. In conclusion, a standardised definition of "injury" is needed to assess FFT, and until more valid indicators of animal welfare regarding "suffering" are developed, the ABIs suggested in animal welfare science (e.g. Welfare Quality) are the most suited for use in practice.

In order to decide which indicators should be reviewed in depth, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has researched for candidate indicators of FFT.

In the first place, the three indicators specifically listed by the *Council Regulation (EC 1/2005)* were considered:

- Inability to move without pain or to walk unassisted
- Severe open wounds
- Prolapses

Other ABIs are not so clearly defined by the Regulation but are related to injuries or other negative welfare consequences. They have been discussed in literature for broilers or for laying hens and are listed in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. Other indicators for the assessment of fitness for transport found in literature.

Indicator	Reference
Broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022; Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017; RSPCA, 2017)
Emaciation and cachexia	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; EFSA et al., 2022; Grandin, 2019; Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017; Jacobs et al., 2017; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017)
Evident signs of illness	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022; Grandin, 2019; Hennovation, Temple, Weeks, et al., 2017; Jacobs et al., 2017; OIE, 2018; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017; RSPCA, 2017)
Poor feather cover (in low effective temperature)	(EFSA et al., 2022)
Wet plumage (in low effective temperature)	(Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017)
Fatigued or exhausted	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; OIE, 2018; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017; RSPCA, 2017)
Keel bone damage	EURCAW-Poultry-SFA
Dehydrated	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024)
Foot Pad Dermatitis	(Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017)
Skin lesions (including breast blisters or bruises)	(Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017)
Splayed legs	(Grandin, 2019)
Hock burn	(Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017)
Plumage cleanliness	(Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017)
Hernia	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024)
Blind in both eyes	(Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; OIE, 2018)

“Evident signs of illness” is not a single indicator but a set of indicators. As mentioned above, illness is a factor limiting the coping capacity for hens during transport. In broilers, for example,

infectious diseases and cardiovascular disorders contribute to the risk of mortality during transport to slaughter (Cockram, 2019).

EFSA et al. (2022) considers that illness' indicators include: distressed breathing; diarrhoea; neurological symptoms; hunched posture (or crouched posture); ascites (dilated abdomen/oedema). But it also considers further indicators as moribund (unable to or struggling to move when approached; having swollen, puffy heads and sinuses; dark red, purple or black combs or wattles).

Poultry Service Association et al. (2017) also consider other general signs of illness like: weak, not alert or moribund animal; other evident signs of respiratory disease i.e. discharge from eyes or nostrils; swollen head or neck; abnormal colouring of the skin (dark red or very pale).

Grandin (2019) and Jacobs et al. (2017) add these two: body temperature; physical defects.

Canada Health of Animals Legislation (2024) also includes: signs of hyperthermia or hypothermia; signs of fever; shock or dying animal.

9 Selected indicators to consider laying hens unfit for transport

Not all the candidate ABIs have been included in this review, for different reasons explained below. In addition, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has also reclassified or renamed indicators in order to encompass all the information from literature and avoid duplication of the same indicator when similar terms have been encountered to describe a similar situation. This selection has been made based on the literature and expert opinion of the authors.

The indicator "Inability to walk without pain or to walk unassisted" (*Council Regulation EC 1/2005*) is defined as "Severe lameness: unable to stand or walk more than a few steps" by EFSA et al. (2022). This is the definition that EURCAW-Poultry-SFA decided to use in the present review, as it represents better the birds' situation, so it has been named "Severe lameness".

The indicator "Severe open wounds" includes skin lesions and foot pad lesions, but "Foot pad dermatitis" is a broiler condition that does not apply to laying hens as it is. Foot pad dermatitis consists of, by definition, a contact dermatitis found on the skin of the foot, most commonly on the central pad, but sometimes also on the toes. Laying hens can usually have other kind of wounds in the foot pads like hyperkeratosis, inflammation of subcutaneous tissue, swelling or ulceration in addition to foot pad dermatitis. These terms will be covered and discussed in the section "11.1 Severe open wounds". "Breast blisters" mostly apply to broilers and it has not been discussed in particular, but it would also be considered as a wound if encountered in a laying hen.

"Hock burns" and "Splayed legs" are also conditions that mostly apply to broilers, so they have not been included in this review.

“Body temperature” has been discarded because it requires additional tools to assess it (i.e. a thermographic camera or thermometer), meaning that currently it is not practical for all inspections in real conditions.

Some birds are apparently “Fatigued or exhausted” (either before transport or when they arrive at the slaughterhouse), probably related to food and water withdrawal. However, these indicators are vague and difficult to assess and more a resultant of transport than farming conditions, so they have not been included for review.

“Plumage cleanliness” is an indicator linked to wet plumage. “Dirtiness” *per se* is not a problem for the transport of EoL hens, except if it causes hens to be wet in cold weather. For this reason, it is not included as an indicator, but dirtiness is discussed in the indicator “Wet plumage” if it entails the animal to be wet.

Regarding the “Evident signs of illness” set of indicators, all obvious clinical signs of illness should be considered. However, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has decided to use the following categories that encompass the different ones presented above in literature:

- Signs of respiratory disease, including distressed breathing and discharge from the eyes or nostrils
- Diarrhoea
- Signs of general infection, including abnormal colouring of the skin (dark red or very pale), other physical defects.
- Ascites (dilated abdomen/oedema)
- Neurological symptoms, including hunched posture or crouched posture.
- Moribund animal, including weak or clearly fatigued, not alert, swollen head or neck, abnormal colouring of the comb or wattles (dark red, purple or black).

The indicators “Blind in both eyes” and “Hernia” appear in the literature related mostly to bigger animals. Birds with hernia or blind in both eyes are scarce. If encountered, they should be considered unfit for transport. Other situations not described in the literature or in the previous list of indicators may be encountered during FFT assessments, and veterinary advice should be asked for when there is any doubt. However, the authors of this review considered unnecessary to discuss other indicators if they are not listed above.

Indicators of flock health

There are many indicators that help to identify if the flock is, in general, in good health (e.g. mortality, weight uniformity, sneezing, or general state of the animals). If a flock is diagnosed with a disease by a veterinarian or laboratory, it shall be discussed if transportation to the slaughterhouse could be avoided. However, this review will not address indicators of general health of the flock, as it focusses on indicators of FFT for animals at an individual level.

Monitoring at slaughter: Dead on Arrival

There is an indicator that has been frequently linked to fitness for transport without being *per se* an indicator of fitness: Dead on Arrival. DoA is considered a key indicator of welfare during

transport (L. Jacobs et al., 2017b) because any animal that dies in transit can be expected to have experienced some degree of suffering before death (Vecerkova et al., 2019). It must be recorded by the official veterinarians at the slaughterhouse for broiler chickens (*Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007*, laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production). DoA is defined as the percentage of birds found dead in the container (i.e. uncontrolled death of birds) at uncrating (expressed as %DoA) (EFSA et al., 2022; Fuseini et al., 2023). These animals have died during the time between loading and the end of lairage. %DoA represent an economic loss and a welfare concern, and it is considered an iceberg indicator because it provides information of the severity of animal welfare issues experienced by the birds during their journey to slaughter and lairage (Cockram & Dulal, 2018; EFSA et al., 2022). The main welfare consequences leading to DoA are heat stress, cold stress and the conditions of the animals (i.e. unfitness for transport) (EFSA et al., 2022) and also long travel distances and light body weight (Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Moe, et al., 2023). It is also correlated to on-farm mortality but is known to be even more related to transport than to farming conditions (EFSA et al., 2022).

Even though it is clear that DoA is linked to FFT, this indicator has not been included in this review because it cannot be used to select unfit animals before transportation. However, DoA is useful for inspection purposes at slaughterhouses, meaning that when it is assessed for each transport, it can be used as an iceberg indicator of the transport conditions. In fact, EFSA et al. (2022) states that it is usual for CAs to have determined a DoA threshold (at least for broilers) above which an investigation takes place to try to determine the cause/s. EFSA et al. (2022) suggested that this threshold might be 0.1% for all domestic birds.

Monitoring at slaughter: other indicators

Some indicators are easier to assess at the slaughter line, when the bird is featherless (e.g. skin lesions). That's why monitoring at slaughter can be a good tool to evaluate welfare (e.g. using the LEGMONI Protocol), and to detect producers who may be sending birds unfit for transport. It is not the scope of this review to show the assessment of indicators at slaughter, as FFT shall be assessed on-farm. However, if we encountered a methodology to assess a given indicator at slaughter, it is also presented in order to give complementary information.

Other indicators that may be relevant at slaughter but not on-farm (e.g. bruising, stocking density in crates, supine birds in crates, DoA, pericarditis, hepatitis...) are not included in the review.

Summary: final list of indicators

The final list of ABIs is:

- Severe open wounds
- Prolapses
- Severe lameness
- Broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations
- Keel Bone Damage
- Emaciation and cachexia
- Dehydration
- Evident signs of illness

- Poor feather cover (in low effective temperature)
- Wet plumage (in low effective temperature)

10 Methodology for review

The literature review has been carried out through an online search for information related to the topics of "fitness for transport", "welfare assessment", "animal-based indicators", "animal-based measures", "catching", "loading", "handling", "depopulation", "physiology" in "domestic birds", "poultry", "turkeys", "broilers", "chickens", "laying hens", "layers", "layer hens", "end of lay hens", "end of cycle laying hens", and other production species (pigs, rabbits, bovidae and equidae animals) in English.

Google search engine has been used for the research of general information, guidelines, handbooks, manuals or guides, best practices documents and protocols. Some physical books have also been reviewed for general information or for physiological definitions of the indicators. On the other hand, Web of Science and Google Scholar were used for reviewing the selected ABIs. The principal key words used for this purpose are "hen", "end of lay hen", "end of cycle hen", "spent hen", "laying hen," "broiler," "chicken," "poultry," in combination with other search terms found in [Table 2](#). Moreover, as usual, additional articles were accumulated throughout the data extraction process, by following citations of cited papers (snowballing).

The selected ABIs have been described in detail in section 11 and, for each of them, the following sections have been covered:

- Description of the indicator
- Description of the available methods for their assessment, either on farm or at slaughter
- Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport
- Gaps of knowledge

Furthermore, European legislation has been also consulted, as well as some documents from the Animal Transport Guides Project, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and Flanders institute (ILVO).

Finally, references have been managed with the reference management software EndNote 21.

Table 2. List of search terms used in combination with the key words to find specific information about each selected ABI.

FFT ABIs	Specific search terms
Severe open wounds	"skin lesion"; "open wound"; "open wounds"
Prolapses	"cloacal prolapse"; "animal prolapse"; "prolapse"
Lameness	"lameness"; "gait score"; "walking ability"; "latency to lie"; "inability to move"
Broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations	"wing fracture"; "broken wing"; "wing dislocation"; "leg dislocation"; "dislocated joint"; "dislocation"; "leg fracture"; "broken leg"; "limb fracture"; "fractures"; "toe damage"
Keel bone damage	"keel bone damage"; "keel bone fracture"; "keel bone deviation"; "sternum fracture"
Emaciation and cachexia	"emaciation"; "cachexia"; "body condition"; "poor body condition"; "body weigh"; "body weight loss"
Dehydration	"dehydration"; "water deprivation"; "water"
Signs of respiratory disease	"respiratory disease"; "respiratory signs"; "respiratory symptoms"; "distressed breathing"
Diarrhoea	"diarrhoea"; "diarrhoea"; "flushing"
Ascites	"ascites"; "ascites syndrome"; "water belly"; "pulmonary arterial hypertension"; "pulmonary arterial hypertension"
Neurological symptoms	"neurological signs", "neurological symptoms", "neurological disease", "ataxia", "tremor", "paralysis", "circling", "nervous system", "difficulty walking", "head twisting" "neck twisting", "convulsions", "torticollis", "spams"
Moribund	"moribund"; "dying";
Poor feather plumage	"feather condition"; "feather pecking"; "poor feather cover"; "feather score"
Wet plumage	"wet plumage"; "wet animal"

11 Indicators of fitness for transport

11.1 Severe open wounds

Description of the indicator:

Wounds comprise all lesions to the skin which are not yet completely healed. They range from minor superficial punctiform spots, to scratches, to large open wounds that go deeper than the skin (Welfare Quality Network, 2019). The indicator also includes abscesses and some foot injuries, but it does not include bruises, bone lesions (thus wing fractures) or beak issues.

The physical damage to the integument or underlying tissues (e.g. multiple scratches, open or scabbed wounds, bruises, ulcers or abscesses) brings the animal to experience negative affective states such as discomfort, pain and/or distress (EFSA et al., 2022).

Wounds can be classified in many ways, based upon their size, depth, severity, degree of healing, location, age of the lesion and aetiology (Ontario Farm Animal Council et al., 2012; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017; Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Equidae, 2015; Practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of pigs, 2015).

In literature, concerning poultry, wounds are usually grouped according to their location: "skin lesions", "foot pad lesions", "toe damage" and "comb pecking wounds" (Welfare Quality Network, 2019)(see definitions in [Table 3](#)).

Table 3: Definitions of wound categories in laying hens.

Indicator	Definition
Skin lesions	Wounds in the rear part (rump, tail, and belly) and legs of the animal that have not yet completely healed (Welfare Quality Network, 2019).
Foot pad lesions	Wounds that can appear in the form of hyperkeratosis (defined as "excessive growth, thickening of the stratum corneum/outermost layer of the epidermis" (Healthy Hens, 2014) or foot pad dermatitis (defined as "a condition that causes necrotic lesions on the plantar surface of the footpads" (Shepherd & Fairchild, 2010)) with inflamed subcutaneous tissue followed by necrosis and ulceration or "bumble foot", with bulbous lesions and swelling (Grafl et al., 2017). "Bumble foot" is associated with a deeper infection producing calluses and hyperplastic tissue formation, culminating in the characteristic "balling" of the foot (Grist, 2006).
Toe damage	Wounds on one or more toes and/or missing (parts of) one or more toes (Welfare Quality Network, 2019).
Comb pecking wounds	Wounds in the comb caused by pecking that are not healed (Welfare Quality Network, 2019).

"Toe damage" can be understood and scored as an open wound when there is an open fracture with fresh blood or as a broken bone when one or more toes are missing. In this document, this wound category will be included on the broken legs scope and the methods described for its

assessment will be covered later, in the section 11.4 “broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations”.

“Comb pecking wounds” are not considered, by the authors of this review on the basis of Chapter 1 of Annex 1 of *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005 of 22 December 2004*, to constitute a reason for declaring birds unfit for transport. Therefore, they are not further developed in this report.

However, to assess FFT, the most useful classification is one which considers together the size, the depth, the severity, and the degree of healing of a wound, rather than the location. In accordance with this, wounds can be classified to “minor open wounds” and “severe open wounds” according to the following definitions used in other species.

“Minor open wounds” will comprise any wound which is almost healed and at no risk of reopening as well as small non-severe superficial wounds or scratches where only the skin is affected and the blood flow is very limited, without risk of major haemorrhage (Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Adult Bovines, 2012). “Severe open wounds” encompass the types of injuries described below (Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Adult Bovines, 2012; Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Equidae, 2015):

- Any sizable wound where integrity of the body surface is seriously destroyed. Skin, muscles, or mucous membranes may be severed, and bone or deeper tissue exposed. The internal organs (intestines, stomach, etc) may be visible from the outside.
- A sizable, infected open wound (sore) with symptoms of inflammation (swelling, redness, and certain pain) and possibly accompanied by the presence of pus or maggots.
- A large healing wound that has reopened.
- A wound which causes inability to move, difficulty moving or do not allow to bare weight on both legs.
- An open abscess (ruptured abscess realising pus).

Description of the method:

The existing methods of assessing wounds in poultry are based on the location of the wound and are mostly useful for assessing animal welfare on farm. The methods give a score based on the size and number of lesions the animal has.

To assess **skin lesions** at farm, live birds are held individually and examined for the presence of skin body lesions that have not yet completely healed. Usually, they become more apparent when the bird has lost many feathers. To obtain the score (for on-farm methods) all regions specified in each scoring method are checked and the worst score is noted (see Table 4).

Skin lesions can also be assessed at the slaughterhouse. The method used for this is presented in Table 5 and, when using it, the number of injuries in the different zones is added up for each hen.

Table 4: Methods for assessing skin lesions on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
LayWel Project et al. (2006)	Wounds	Score 1-2-3 for wounds on rear (no definition, just photographic reference)	Yes
Healthy Hens and Bestman (2012)	Injurious pecking	<i>Belly (including cloaca), back (including rump) and tail are examined.</i> Score 1: wound > 2,2 cm Score 2: wound < 2,2 cm Score 3: diameter wound < 0,5 cm or haematoma. Blood filled follicles after a feather was pulled out, is no wound Score 4: no wounds at all	Yes
Welfare Quality Network (2019)	Skin lesions	<i>Rump, tail, belly and legs are examined.</i> Score 0: no lesions, only single (<3) pecks (punctiform damage <0.5 cm diameter) or scratches Score 1: at least one lesion ≥0.5 cm <2 cm diameter at largest extent or ≥3 pecks or scratches Score 2: at least one lesion ≥2 cm diameter at largest extent	Yes
Özentürk et al. (2023)	Integument damage	<i>Comb and cloaca are examined.</i> Score 1: Single or multiple injuries of >1.0 cm Score 2: Multiple injuries of <0.5 cm or single injuries of >0.5 cm and <1.0 cm Score 3: Single injury of <0.5 cm diameter or length Score 4: No integument damage	No

Table 5: Method for assessing skin lesions on slaughterhouse described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
LEGMONI Project et al. (2024)	Injuries	<i>Back, breast, belly and cloaca are examined.</i> Score 1: injurie(s) > 2,2 cm Score 2: injurie(s) between 0,5 and 2,2 cm Score 3: > 2 injuries, <0,5 cm Score 4: no or ≤ 2 small injuries	No

To assess **foot pad lesions** on farm, live birds are picked up individually and both feet are visually examined. On the slaughter line, foot pad lesions are assessed immediately after scalding and before the feet are cut off. The more severe score is noted for each animal. In [Tables 6 and 7](#) the scoring scales for assessing foot pad lesions (at farm and slaughter) are presented.

Table 6: Methods for assessing foot pad lesions on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
LayWel Project et al. (2006)	Bumble foot syndrome	Score 1-2-3 for bumble foot syndrome (no description, just photographic reference)	Yes
Healthy Hens (2014)	Foot pad hyperkeratosis	Score 1: hyperkeratosis Score 2: no hyperkeratosis	Yes

Healthy Hens (2014)	Foot pad lesions	Score 1: dorsal swelling Score 2: larger lesion > 0,2 cm Score 3: small lesion < 0.2 cm (e.g. size of a pin head) Score 4: No lesion.	Yes
Welfare Quality Network (2019)	Foot pad lesions	Score 0: feet intact, no or minimal proliferation of epithelium, no wounds Score 1: necrosis or proliferation of epithelium or chronic bumble foot with no or moderate swelling, not dorsally visible Score 2: swollen (dorsally visible).	Yes

Table 7: Methods for assessing foot pad lesions on slaughterhouse described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (2022a)	Foot lesions	Score 0: no lesion, feet intact, no or minimal epithelium proliferation, no bumble foot Score 1: moderate lesions of the feet, epithelium proliferation with no or moderate swelling Score 2: severe lesions, necrosis, and/or bumble foot (swollen foot dorsally visible)	Yes
LEGMONI Project et al. (2024)	Footpad dermatitis	Score 1: deep and big lesion and moderate or severe swelling Score 2: deep lesion (>2mm) and/or mild swelling Score 3: superficial lesion (≤2mm) and no swelling Score 4: intact and no swelling	No

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

In the *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005 of 22 December 2004* it is specified that birds with severe open wounds are unfit for transport. As mentioned above, the assessment methods addressed in Tables 6 and 7 are accurate for determining the repercussion that wounds have on birds' welfare. However, these methods are not useful when wounds are assessed in terms of animal FFT since, in this case, it is recommended to consider the possibilities for deterioration, their potential to become infected, to cause pain and severe blood loss during transport, as well as if they allow the bird to bear weight on both legs (Herskin et al., 2021; Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Equidae, 2015; Practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of pigs, 2015). In this sense, in Herskin et al. (2021), Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Adult Bovines (2012) and Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Equidae (2015) it is stated that the characteristics to consider when assessing wounds in the FFT context are the size and/or the severity of the wound, its depth, its location, the degree of healing, and the number of wounds.

As a result, birds with healed or minor abrasions or scratches, without risk of major haemorrhage, can be considered fit for transport (KIPVANG Project et al., 2023). Nonetheless, in pigs, it is described that animals with these conditions must be isolated, marked, loaded last, the food chain informed, and the transport should not cause unnecessary pain or suffering (Practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of pigs, 2015). Animals with serious open wounds (e.g. wounds that penetrate all skin layers, or that also damage the underlying tissue, severe skin tears and lacerations involving all skin layers that are unhealed, or wounds that are infected, inflamed or with signs of possible necrosis) are unfit for transport (EFSA et al., 2022; Practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of pigs, 2015).

Gaps of knowledge:

- The criteria and definitions used for FFT have been established for other species (horses, pigs, and bovine animals) and sometimes they are imprecise (i.e. using the terms “sizable” or “large”).
- Although there are multiple scoring methods validated for laying hens on farm for assessing wounds in relation to animal welfare, there is no scoring method for assessing wounds in terms of FFT.
- Even if the described methods are used, there isn’t a threshold to differentiate if the animal is fit or unfit.
- There are still some cases where further assessment might be necessary before assigning the animal as unfit or fit for transport e. g. birds with an abscess that has not ruptured – which may cause more pain than an open one–, with several wounds, or with a wound that may reopen (Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Equidae, 2015).
- Some wounds could not be seen without catching the birds. This can be time consuming, so an assessment strategy should be discussed.

11.2 Prolapses

Description of the indicator:

Prolapse concerns a condition where an organ or viscus is protruding from the body (Herskin et al., 2021; Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021). In laying hens, the most relevant prolapses are cloacal prolapses, also known as “prolapsed oviduct”, “prolapsed vent” or “blowout”. They specifically consist of the displacement of the lower part of the hen’s oviduct through the vent or cloaca (*Manual Merck de Veterinaria*, 2008; Poultry Service Association et al., 2017; Ray et al., 2013). However, rectal prolapses can also occur in laying hens. They consist of the protrusion of all layers of the rectum through the vent as an elongated cylindrical mass (Ray et al., 2013). As a result, the unprotected and protruding organ tissue becomes susceptible to be damaged or pecked, meaning the animal can also be injured and develop an infection (EFSA et al., 2022).

If a bird with a prolapse is not isolated on time, other birds might peck at its vent causing extreme prolapse and severe damage. In these cases, the bird is unlikely to recover and should be euthanized (Jacob, 2024).

Description of the method:

There are no methods described for assessing prolapses in poultry. However, in Yngvesson et al. (2004) cloacal prolapses are indirectly assessed by a 4-point scale used for assessing cloacal wounds in hens from commercial farms (Table 8). Hens are collected and examined individually. The cloaca is assessed looking for scabs, peck wounds or prolapse.

Table 8: Method for assessing cloacal wounds on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Yngvesson et al. (2004)	Cloacal wounds	Score 1: normal cloaca Score 2: a cloaca with a scab Score 3: a cloaca with peck wounds Score 4: prolapse	No

For pigs, the Welfare Quality Network (2009a) provides an assessment method for rectal and uterine prolapses. Sows and piglets are examined from the rear checking for the presence of swelling or extrusion of tissue from the rectum or, in the case of sows, also the presence of the extrusion of the uterus from the vagina. The animals are given a score according to the presence/absence of rectal/uterine prolapse (Score 0: no evidence of prolapse; Score 2: evidence of prolapse). No photos are provided in the written protocol, but usually are provided in the training courses. EURCAW-Pigs also provided a factsheet about prolapses with photographic examples of the problem (EURCAW-Pigs, 2021).

In order to assess the presence or absence of this problem in laying hens, a definition is needed. Ray et al. (2013) provides a theoretical description of the indicator (see above, 'description of the indicator'). The Indian technical Journal, Dash (2023) gives a more practical description with photographic references, saying that a prolapsed oviduct is a vent that looks like its insides are falling out, which may also have blood and faeces on the feathers around it. EFSA et al. (2022) also provides a photographic reference for this indicator. Moreover, if the bird has been picked at by other birds, tissue might be missing, leaving a bloody gaping hole. The *Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual* (2019) states that in prolapsed birds, the area under the tail will have exposed red tissue that appears to stick out, and there can also be blood in the area.

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

In the *Council Regulation (EC 1/2005)* is specified that animals that present a prolapse are unfit for transport. Prolapsed organs can be easily damaged during transport which can lead to painful profuse bleeding and further infection (EFSA et al., 2022; Practical Guidelines to Assess Fitness for Transport of Adult Bovines, 2012). For these reasons any hen with a prolapse or blood coming out from the cloaca is unfit for transport (KIPVANG Project et al., 2023).

Gaps of knowledge:

- There are not specific methods to score prolapses in laying hens, but descriptions are available to assess them. As this problem is either present or absent in the bird, a 2-scale scoring system could be adapted for FFT using the existing descriptions of the term.
- The existing methods for assessment rely on visual inspection of the cloacal area, meaning that handling the bird may be necessary. This can be time consuming, so an assessment strategy should be discussed.

11.3 Severe lameness

Description of the indicator:

Lameness is the inability to use one or both limbs in a normal manner, and it can range from reduced to total inability to bear weight (i.e. immobility) (Welfare Quality Network, 2009b). Severe lameness corresponds to an abnormal gait and an inability or an extreme difficulty for animals to stand on both legs and/or walk. Its causes are numerous: they can be infectious, metabolic, due to developmental deformities, etc, and mostly related to pain. However, the link between lameness and the severity of the pain probably depends on the cause of lameness (for example, contractures of joints, deformities or shortness of limbs are not linked to pain) (EFSA, 2010; Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021). But even without consensus on pain experienced by them, it's clear that the welfare of the birds will be compromised if, for example, they are less capable of reaching the feeders or drinkers.

Lameness has been studied much more thoroughly for broilers than for laying hens, as genetic growth rates are a major risk factor for lameness (Jacobs et al., 2017). However, as in broilers, it is associated with production efficiency, welfare status, bone quality, physiology and metabolism, because it is directly linked to the ability to access resources (Li et al., 2023).

Description of the method:

There is an absence of specific methods for assessment for laying hens, as most of the research in this topic has been made for broilers. However, for broilers numerous methods exist to assess lameness and walking ability. They have been included as they could also be relevant for laying hens in the context of FFT even if they are not validated for laying hens.

Gait scoring is the most widely used, due to its ease of implementation on farm. However, other methods, for which the equipment or training required differ, have been investigated as well. These methods, which are increasingly used to supplant gait scoring (which is deemed too subjective), comprise: latency to lie tests, obstacle courses and kinematic or kinetic approaches, as well as the assessment of activity levels (Wurtz & Riber, 2024).

Table 9 summarises the main methods used to assess lameness in broilers. Gait scoring is an empirical method consisting of visually observing of animals as they walk across a surface and assigning a numerical rating of the bird's locomotory ability, for example on a scale from 0 to 5

(although many gait scoring systems exist). This method is commonly referred to as the Bristol scale. The Welfare Quality Assessment Protocol for poultry includes a gait scoring method for broilers, which is very similar to the Bristol scale (Welfare Quality Network, 2009b) that is widely used, but other methods are based on the Bristol scale with small differences in the score descriptions (e.g. RSPCA (2017)). It is recommended that, at least, two individuals conduct a farm gait-scoring audit, one to handle the birds and the other to record gait scores after observing animals from the side (Webster et al., 2008). Other scales than 6 point-scales exist, such as the 3-point scoring system developed by the National Chicken Council for use in welfare audits within the United States (*National Chicken Council Broiler Welfare Guidelines and Audit Checklist*, 2022). It appeared to be more consistent between observers, and simpler to use than the 6-point scales (Webster et al., 2008).

Nonetheless, although training can improve scoring accuracy (Butterworth et al., 2007), gait scoring subjectivity can make comparison between farms scored by different observers difficult. For this reason, other methods have been developed. Furthermore, gait scoring implies encouraging birds to walk which may invoke fear or pain and skew gait scores (as even lame birds can walk relatively well under pressure) (Wurtz & Riber, 2024).

“Latency to lie” is a test that consist in recording the amount of time a bird takes to sit, with longer standing durations being associated with better walking ability. Few variations of this test exist, including the use or absence of water as an aversive stimulus, individual or group assessment, or whether the animals are tested in a container or without any restriction in the house. Sitting or lying are postures that remove weight from the birds’ limbs, providing them with relief if they experience pain or discomfort from conditions relating to their legs. Consequently, gait score and latency to lie time have been found to be positively correlated (at least for broilers) (Wurtz & Riber, 2024), although not in all studies (Webster et al., 2008). As opposed to the qualitative and subjective gait scoring, the latency to lie test provides a quantitative time measure (Weeks et al., 2002 as cited in Wurtz & Riber, 2024).

For the purpose of assessing FFT, the latency to lie test without water and without restriction in the house would be the most appropriate (see [Table 9](#)), even if it’s more time consuming than the gait scoring. In addition, more work is needed to assess the test’s validity, reliability, and feasibility (Wurtz & Riber, 2024).

Other methods exist, but they require specific equipment (e.g. force plates, cameras) which make them being not appropriate for FFT inspections (Wurtz & Riber, 2024).

Table 9. Methods for assessing lameness on farm described for broilers that can be used for FFT inspections.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Welfare Quality Network (2009b)	Lameness (gait score)	Score 0. Normal, dextrous and agile. Score 1. Slight abnormality, but difficult to define. Score 2. Definite and identifiable abnormality. Score 3. Obvious abnormality, affects ability to move. Score 4. Severe abnormality, only takes a few steps. Score 5. Incapable of walking.	Yes, but only during the training courses
RSPCA (2017)	Lameness	Score 0. The bird displays smooth, fluid locomotion. Score 1. The bird has a slight defect in its gait that is difficult to define precisely. Score 2. The bird has a definite and identifiable gait abnormality, but this does not affect its ability to move. Score 3. The bird has an obvious gait defect that affects its ability to move (bird welfare is compromised). Score 4. The bird has a severe gait defect. Score 5. The bird is incapable of sustained walking on its feet.	No
<i>National Chicken Council Broiler Welfare Guidelines and Audit Checklist</i> (2022)	Gait scoring	Score 0. Bird can walk at least 5 feet with a balanced gait. Bird may appear ungainly but with no visible signs of lameness. Score 1. Bird can walk at least 5 feet, but appears awkward, uneven in steps. Score 2. Bird cannot walk 5 feet or there is obvious lameness. May shuffle on shanks or hocks with assistance of wings.	No
Baxter et al. (2021)	Latency to lie test without water	The selected lying bird is approached and encouraged to stand. Time until the bird sits back down is recorded using a stopwatch. The test is terminated after the bird sits or 2 min are reached.	No

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

In the *Council Regulation (EC 1/2005)* it is specified that animals with severe lameness are unfit for transport. Therefore, any animal that cannot stand or take more than a few steps should not be loaded (i.e. scores 4-5 of the 6-point scale or score 2 of the 3-point scale). This means that animals that can still walk but show great difficulties, are slow or sit down quickly, cannot stand on both legs or are moving with support of the wings, should also be considered unfit for transport.

It remains unclear if animals with moderate lameness (i.e. score 3 on a 6-point scale) would represent a fit or unfit animal, as they experience pain when walking that will likely increase during transport (as they try to find balance during transport)(EFSA et al., 2022).

Gaps of knowledge:

- There is an absence of specific lameness definition and methods for assessment for laying hens, as most of the research in this topic has been made for broilers.
- When using a 6-point scale, it is unclear if score 3 would represent a fit or unfit animal.
- Even if the gait scoring is deemed too subjective, it's not clear that any alternatives can be used for laying hens. The latency to lie test could be used but it's time consuming and there isn't a threshold to differentiate if the animal is fit or unfit. Besides, more work is needed to assess the test's validity, reliability, and feasibility.
- The existing methods for assessment rely on the handling of the animals. This can be time consuming, so an assessment strategy should be discussed.

11.4 Broken bones (legs, wings) and dislocations

Description of the indicator:

As it is commonly known, a fracture refers to a break in a bone, and it can be closed or open depending on whether it is associated directly with an open wound or not. On the other hand, a dislocation, also called luxation, is defined as the abnormal displacement of a bone from a joint (Baron, 2017).

Fractures and dislocations usually occur in long bones (Ortín et al., 2017). In the context of FFT, "old fractures" refer to the fractures that occurred during the laying period while "new fractures" are the ones that appeared due to catching, transport, or pre-slaughter handling (FAWC, 2010; Ortín et al., 2017).

The incidence of bone fractures in laying hens, both during and at the end of lay, is very high in all husbandry systems, primarily because genetic selection for productivity has resulted in weaker birds, as calcium from the bones is used for the eggshell high demand (Grandin, 2020). The incidence of fractures is determined mainly by i) the demineralization and weakness of bones, resulting mainly from osteoporosis; ii) the design of housing systems, including space availability and layout; and iii) handling at depopulation (FAWC, 2010).

It has been shown in poultry that birds have sensitive pain perception mechanisms and therefore, they are likely to experience pain from bone fractures and dislocations, which will also reduce their mobility (*Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual*, 2019; Knowles & Wilkins, 1998; Welfare Quality Network, 2009b)). They might have inability to walk properly and elevated stress levels, which compromises their immune system and makes them more susceptible to diseases (Ajibola & Erasmus, 2024; Marchewka et al., 2020). Doubtlessly, such extreme physical damage is indicative of an inability to cope with the environment and shows very poor welfare (Knowles & Wilkins, 1998).

Wing fractures are considered as open or closed fractures and detachment of epiphyseal plates with visible bleeding around the elbow joints, dislocated wings or wings hanging straight down, as stated in Grandin, 2010 as cited in Kittelsen et al. (2015).

Additionally, this indicator also includes the following situations:

- Leg fractures, either open or closed fractures in leg bones (femur, tibiotarsus, fibula and tarsometatarsus)
- Toe damage (see [section 11.1](#) for description)
- Hip (coxofemoral articulation), knee (tibiofemoral articulation) or hock (tarsal articulation) dislocations.

Description of the method:

The existing methods for assessing broken bones and dislocations in poultry are described for their use at the slaughterhouse. The methods consist in looking at the animals hung on the shackle line before the stunning phase or paying attention to post-mortem injuries on the carcasses (before scalding).

Generally, the number of birds showing hanging, non-functional limbs or protruding bones are counted (EFSA et al., 2022). Wings might droop toward the ground and legs might stick out at unphysiological angles. Additionally, legs discolored with bruises might also be a sign of broken bones (*Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual*, 2019; LEGMONI Project et al., 2024).

It is difficult to determine for sure if fractures detected prior to slaughter have occurred on farm, during transport or during handling at the slaughterhouse as the presence of feathers may hinder their assessment on live animals. On the other hand, the ones detected after scalding might have happened as well during the scalding. Since the fractures relevant for animal welfare are those that occurred when the animal was alive, the presence of a bruise accompanying the fracture must be observed to distinguish them from post-mortem carcass damage. Moreover, the bruise' colour can help to estimate the time of occurrence ([Table 10](#))(EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2023).

Table 10: Colour of bruises in relation to time since the injury was inflicted (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2023) adapted from Gregory (1992).

Estimate age of contusion	Colours of the bruise
From 2 minutes	Red
From 12 hours	Dark red/ purple
From 24 hours	Light purple*
36 hours	Light green / purple*
48 hours	Yellow – green – purple*
72 hours	Yellow – green*
96 hours	Light yellow*
120 hours	Normal skin color (no visible bruise)

*Most likely to be caused at the farm level.

To assess **broken wings** on the slaughter line, according to Welfare Quality Network (2009b), birds are observed just after they have been hanged on. First, the number of birds passing per minute (line speed: birds/min) must be recorded and then, the number of birds with wings clearly hanging down or with open fractures counted. Finally, the percentage of birds with wing fracture or dislocation according to the total of birds assessed is calculated. The method stated in Grandin (2020) is similar and it also recommends doing the assessment with the feathers on and including also both breaks and dislocations. On the other hand, in Wigham et al. (2019) and Welfair (2023b), the assessment of broken wings is done after scalding and plucking, when carcasses are scored for external quality, considering only the cases that the broken wing has an associated hemorrhage, as this indicates that the damage occurred pre-slaughter. In [Table 11](#) the different available scoring scales for assessing broken wings are presented.

Table 11: Methods for assessing broken wings on slaughterhouse described for poultry.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Welfare Quality Network (2009b)	Wing damage (fractures)	The number of birds with 'dropped wings' is counted. Ante-mortem assessment, when animals are hung on the line.	Yes, but only in the training course
Welfair (2023b)	Wing damage (fractures)	The number of birds with 'dropped wings' is counted. Ante-mortem assessment, when animals are hung on the line. The number of birds with fracture is counted, only if haemorrhage is also present. Postmortem assessment, after.	Yes, but only in the training course
Grandin (2020)	Broken wings	The number of birds with broken or dislocated wings is counted. Ante-mortem assessment, when animals are hung on the line.	No
Wigham et al. (2019)	Broken wings	The number of birds with fracture is counted, only if haemorrhage is also present. Postmortem assessment, after.	No

In relation to **broken legs**, there are no described methods for assessing fractures in leg bones in poultry. However, it is reported that some slaughterhouses for broilers have systems for automatic detection of broken legs, allowing the birds to be processed separately (FAWC, 2010). In any case, broken legs will be linked to lameness (see [section 11.3](#)).

Furthermore, a few methods for assessing **toe damage** (wounds and/or missing toes/claws) are described in literature. Some methods are carried out on farm, where the live birds are picked up individually and both feet are visually examined. Other methods are used on the slaughter line, where toe damage is assessed immediately after slaughter, like for the foot pad dermatitis. The more severe finding between both feet is taken into consideration for scoring the animal according to each scoring method criteria ([Table 12](#) and [13](#)).

Table 12: Methods for assessing toe damage on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Healthy Hens (2014)	Missing toes / claws	Score 1: missing toes/claws Score 2: no missing toes/claws	No
Healthy Hens (2014)	Toe wounds	Score 1: open (fresh wounds) or closed (older) wounds Score 2: no wounds	No
Welfare Quality Network (2019)	Toe damage	Toe damage is defined as wounds on one or more toes and/or missing (parts of) one or more toes. Presence or absence of toe damage is noted for each assessed animal.	No

Table 13: Methods for assessing toe damage on farm described for laying hens or chicken.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (2022a)	Damaged and missing toes	Score 0: no or minimal evidence of damaged toe Score 1: visibly damaged toe Score 2: missing toe	Yes
Marchewka et al. (2020) (experimental conditions)	Toe damage	Score 0: no toe damage Score 1: wounds on one toe or missing (parts of) one toe Score 2: wounds on one or more toes and/or missing (parts of) one or more toes	No

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

Bone fractures and dislocations are among the main conditions that render domestic birds unfit for transport (EFSA et al., 2022).

Several studies have associated these circumstances with an increased risk of DoA and rejects in slaughterhouses (EFSA et al., 2022). Moreover, bones fractures and dislocations are painful, and movement or mechanical pressure applied to the fracture site derived from transport would cause additional pain to the animal (Cockram, 2019; Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017). However, in literature there is no criteria for FFT for animals which have different degrees of severity of toe damage (e.g. scratches, open wound, missing claws or missing toes).

It is not only important to identify birds with broken bones during the productive period in order to treat or cull them humanely (FAWC, 2010), but also in the final laying phase, prior to transport (Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017), to ensure that they will be euthanized on farm if they are unfit (Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; FAWC, 2010).

At the end of lay, hens have weakened bones which are more prone to be fractured or dislocated due to collisions or when carried inverted during catching and loading (EFSA et al., 2022). In addition, if hens have unhealed old breaks, they are likely to be painful during handling (Grandin, 2019). As mentioned before ([section 6](#)), weak bones of EoL hens are prone to break as a result of rough handling, when they are pulled by legs or wings, because bones may fracture even in the absence of collisions *per se*. For this reason, it is of a great importance to handle them carefully

when catching, loading and unloading (Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017). Animals that are injured during capture shall not be loaded (KIPVANG Project et al., 2023). In addition, if a stack of containers falls and animals become unfit during the loading of the truck, they should be unloaded and taken care of (Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017).

Gaps of knowledge:

- There are no on-farm assessment methods described in literature for broken wings and legs in poultry. Some fractures will be apparent (i.e. open fractures) or linked with other indicators (i.e. lameness) but a consistent method of assessment is still needed.
- Regarding broken legs, there is little specification concerning how they are assessed and scored even at the slaughterhouse, leaving the identification of these problems to be done according to the general definition of a broken bone.
- The existing assessment methods for toe damage are useful for determining the repercussion that wounds and missing toes and claws have on animal welfare. However, they are not useful when toe damage is assessed in terms of animal FFT, and thresholds should be provided in order to declare a bird fit or unfit.

11.5 Keel bone damage

Description of the indicator:

The keel is a prominent straight shape bone, situated ventral to the heart, that extends from the sternum and anchors the muscles used for wing motion (Casey-Trott et al., 2015; Welfare Quality Network, 2019). Due to its exposed anatomical position, it is prone to be damaged (Riber & Hinrichsen, 2016).

Keel bone damage is a general term that covers both keel bone fractures (KBF) and keel bone deviations (KBD) (Casey-Trott et al., 2015 as cited in Toscano et al., 2020)). KBF is defined as a complete or partial break in the keel bone which may, or may not, have healed resulting in a callus (Casey-Trott et al., 2015 as cited in EFSA et al., 2023). On the other hand, KBD are any unnatural bending of the keel bone (Casey-Trott et al., 2015 as cited in Toscano et al., 2020)).

Keel bone damage is susceptible to occur before and after ossification of the keel bone at about 35 weeks of age (FAWC, 2010). It may be damaged or broken by collision with other hens or housing equipment, for example when jumping onto a perch and landing, or become deviated due to osteoporosis (weak bones) and/or long-term pressure with poorly designed perches (EFSA et al., 2023; FAWC, 2010; Hinrichsen et al., 2016; Sirovnik et al., 2018; Welfare Quality Network, 2019). In addition, it has been presumed that KBF may also occur due to excessive force from the muscles involved in wing flapping or by the depopulation procedure, independently of high energy collisions (Gerpe et al., 2021).

Similarly to what occurred in limb bones, keel bone damage has been found in all husbandry systems (Baker et al., 2024). Some studies reported that KBF is one of the most common health

problems in layers, with a prevalence that, in some flocks, can reach more than 85% at end of lay (Rufener & Makagon (2020) as cited in Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Moe, et al., 2023) (Riber & Hinrichsen, 2016) (Baker et al., 2024). The very high incidence arises again from the selection for productivity, since keel bone damage seems to be more likely to occur in hens with weaker and calcium insufficient bones (Hinrichsen et al., 2016) (Rufener & Makagon, 2020). Hence, genetics have an influence on the susceptibility to fractures that a hen may have (Gerpe et al., 2021).

There is evidence that birds with KBF may experience acute and chronic pain, and that pain could contribute to decreased mobility and increased mortality (Hinrichsen et al., 2016; Nasr et al., 2012; Petrik et al., 2013; Welfare Quality Network, 2019). Moreover, there is also prove that hens that suffer from keel injuries since early in lay will repeatedly injure the area ((Richards et al., 2011 as cited in Petrik et al., 2013). The regenerative healing process of a fracture starts with an inflammatory response, followed by the formation of a soft callus which later, after ossification, will result in a hard, bony callus (Casey-Trott et al., 2015). However, healed fractures often can result in deformations, which also represent a major welfare issue (Welfare Quality Network, 2019).

Description of the method:

Numerous methods are described in literature to assess keel bone damage. The most common method used for this purpose is palpation. It consists of catching the birds and examining its breast visually and sliding two fingers along the keel bone, feeling for the presence of callus material or other malformations indicative of previous damage on the ventral and lateral surfaces and paying as well particular attention to the tip of the keel (Casey-Trott et al., 2015; Welfare Quality Network, 2019). Even it is relatively simple and low-cost to carry out, it requires training to ensure that the results are reliable and accurate but, still, it is likely that a percentage of fractures and deviations will be missed (Baur et al., 2020; Casey-Trott et al., 2015; Rufener et al., 2018). Moreover, usually, KBF and KBD are difficult to distinguish when keels are examined externally (Welfare Quality Network, 2019)

Other existing methods of assessing keel bone damage are radiography, ultrasonography and peripheral quantitative computed tomography (Casey-Trott et al., 2015). Some protocols have been developed for these techniques (e.g. Rufener et al. (2018); Sandilands et al., 2010 as cited in Casey-Trott et al. (2015); Baker et al. (2024). Even if these methods are more reliable, they are not as convenient as the palpation method for the assessment of keel bone damage on-farm in a FFT context. For this reason, in this document, only the scoring scales used for assessing keel bone damage by palpation or visual inspection are presented in [Table 14](#) and [15](#).

Table 14: Palpation methods for assessing keel bone damage on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Healthy hens (2014)	Keel bone fracture	Score 1: Fracture Score 2: No fracture	Yes
Healthy hens (2014)	Keel bone deviation	Score 1: Deviation > 1 cm Score 2: > 0,5 cm ≤ 1 cm	Yes

			Score 3: No deviation: straight or deviation $\leq 0,5$ cm	
Healthy hens (2014)		Keel bone tip	Score 1: Deviated Score 2: Not deviated	No
Healthy hens (2014)		Keel bone skin	Score 1: Haematomas on keel bone crest Score 2: No haematomas	Yes
Simplified Assessment Protocol (SKAP) (Casey-Trott et al., 2015)	Keel	Keel bone damage	Deviation and fracture Deviation and no fracture No deviation and fracture No deviation and no fracture	No
Hinrichsen et al. (2016)		Keel bone fracture	Score 1: present Score 2: absent	No, but based on the Healthy Hens scoring protocol
Hinrichsen et al. (2016)		Keel bone deviation	Score 1: > 1 cm Score 2: $0,5 \text{ cm} \geq \leq 1$ cm Score 3: $\leq 0,5$ cm	No, but based on the Healthy Hens scoring protocol
Welfare Network (2019)	Quality	Keel bone damage	Score 0: No deviations, deformations or thickened sections, keel bone completely Straight Score 1: Deviations (flattening, s-shape, bending) or thickened sections present in very slight form Score 2: Deviation or deformation of keel bone (including thickened sections)	Yes

Table 15: Palpation methods for assessing keel bone damage on slaughterhouse described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Scholz (2007) (post-mortem, after dissection)	Keel bone status (according to the severity of deviations)	Score 1: Severe deformity Score 2: Moderate deformity Score 3: Slight deformity Score 4: No deformity	No
Wilkins et al. (2011) (post-mortem, after dissection)	Keel damage severity	By reference to a 5-point photographic scale.	Yes
LEGMONI Project et al. (2024) (Post-mortem assessment)	Keel bone fractures	Present Absent	Yes
LEGMONI Project et al. (2024) (Post-mortem assessment)	Keel bone deviations	Present: there is a bend that deviates more than $0,5$ cm from a straight line. Absent: there is no bend or a deviation of $< 0,5$ cm	Yes

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

Regarding keel bone damage, there is no official criteria for fitness for transport. Literature (*Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual*, 2019; Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project, 2017; EFSA et al., 2022; Grandin, 2019; Jacobs et al., 2017; RSPCA, 2017) specify “legs and wings” when they state that hens with broken bones are unfit for transport and must be humanely euthanized on farm.

However, since any bone fracture may be painful and some deviations too, EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is of the opinion that keel bone damage should be considered when assessing hens for FFT. Another reason for taking it into account is that EoL hens may be already in a state of compromised health due to its special situation mentioned previously and unhealed breaks they may have in the keel bone could mean additional pain and stress during handling and transport. However, no thresholds exist to decide if a bird is fit or unfit.

Catching and loading logistics on farm makes unfeasible to perform an individual accurate assessment of the keel bone damage on that phase (Michel V. and Ribalta J. personal communication, 2024). Nevertheless, at least birds that have impaired mobility due to the keel bone damage must be declared unfit for transport as it is stated in the legislation.

Gaps of knowledge:

- The existing palpation assessment methods for keel bone damage on live animals can be useful for determining the repercussion that deviations and breaks on the keel bone have on animal welfare. However, they may not be practical when keel bone damage is assessed in terms of animal FFT.
- In case of determining the FFT of a bird depending on the severity of a KBF, there is a need to define and set a more practical assessment method since the current ones are either not sensible enough assessing presence/absence or combine the assessment of both KBF and KBD. Moreover, thresholds should be provided in order to declare a bird fit or unfit.
- The existing methods for assessment rely on palpation or visual inspection of the keel bone, meaning that handling of the animals is expected. This can be time consuming, so an assessment strategy should be discussed.

11.6 Emaciation and cachexia

Description of the indicator:

Emaciation is a pathological condition relative to birds in state of extreme malnutrition, which consists in general retrogression in body condition, muscular atrophy, diminution of the size of the organs, and loss of intermuscular tissue and internal fats (Ortín et al., 2017; Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021). Emaciation is a frequent cause of whole carcass condemnation for laying hens and broilers in the inspection lines of processing plants (Nery et al., 2017) (Çavuşoğlu & Petek, 2021; Saraiva et al., 2021) and low body weight has been associated with an increased risk of DoA in EoL hens (Weeks et al., 2012). Emaciation is often secondary to

a primary cause (Saraiva et al., 2021) (Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Moe, et al., 2023) and, along with the presence of small organs, it suggests: malnutrition, beak injury, pecking problems, chronic disease (coccidiosis), bumblefoot or lameness (preventing the bird from accessing the feeders), or chronic poisoning (lead, insecticide, etc.) (Avian Disease Manual, 2013).

Cachexia is the term used to describe the end stage of emaciation (Ford & Mazaferro, 2012). However, some publications give slightly different interpretations of the term, describing it as a metabolic syndrome associated with underlying illness and characterised by loss of muscle with or without loss of fat mass (Jacobs et al., 2017) or by saying that emaciation is associated with the presence of disease whereas cachexia is not (Saraiva et al., 2021). Emaciation and cachexia are terms often indistinctly used or misused in poultry inspection, referring in practice to the same signs of extreme devoid of fat and reduced skeletal muscle on the bird. In this document, the term used in the original source will be kept when describing the methods.

Another term linked to this indicator is "runts", which refers to birds that are significantly smaller than the flock average and which should be culled on farm or rejected ante-mortem at the slaughterhouse (Part et al., 2016). Runts are also defined as "small, stunted, weak", or undersized birds (Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021). Runts can be associated with a genetic dwarfing gene which, in this case, they would not present protrusion of the sternum keel due to the loss of muscle cover, neither the almost complete absence of fat in the carcass (Nery et al., 2017), although unusual. Runts are mostly linked to previous conditions leading to undersize or weakness compromising their access to the feed through.

Description of the method:

Emaciation and cachexia can be evaluated related to the body condition score by estimating keel bone prominence by manual palpation (EFSA et al., 2022) or visual observation if plumage is absent from the breast, with various scoring methods used in different articles (see [Table 16](#)). When assessing the EoL hens' keel bone by palpation, the following should be taking into account: the protuberance of the keel, the development of the breast muscles immediately alongside the ventral ridge of the keel, and the convexity or concavity of the breast muscle contour (Gregory & Robins, 1998). Laying hens specially at the end of laying period are a lean type of bird, meaning that some keel bone prominence is normal (Welfare Quality Network, 2019).

In some cases, a scoring method for this indicator is not provided, but a clear definition of what should be seen to consider an animal emaciated or cachexic (so, presence or absence of the indicator). These descriptions are shown in [Table 17](#). However, they are usually used in post-mortem evaluation.

Table 16: Methods for assessing body condition score on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Gregory and Robins (1998)	Body condition score	<p><u>Score 0</u>: prominent ridge on the keel with limited overall breast muscle and concavity of the breast muscle alongside the keel.</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: greater development of breast muscle which was not concave and was usually flat in contour.</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: moderately developed convex breast muscle.</p> <p><u>Score 3</u>: well-developed relatively plump breast.</p>	No
KIPVANG Project et al. (2023)	Body Condition score	<p><u>Score 0</u>: very lean and weak bird. The sternum is very easy to feel. The muscles dive into the sternum (hollow chest muscle) on the side.</p> <p><u>Scores 1-2-3</u> described in images. Score 1 is lean but still normal. Scores 2 and 3 are healthy animals.</p>	Yes
Welfare Quality Network (2019)	Keel bone prominence	<p>Laying hens are a lean type of bird, meaning that some keel bone prominence is normal. A bird with normal body condition will have some breast muscles present. Emaciated birds hardly have any breast muscle tissue left and have a very edged and prominent keel bone.</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: normal (smooth to moderate breast muscle contour with keel).</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: slightly to moderate prominent keel, but does not feel sharp, flat breast muscle.</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: severely prominent keel, depressed contour to breast muscle.</p>	Yes, for brown or white hens separately
<i>Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual</i> (2019)	Body condition score	<p><u>Score 0</u>: emaciated, very thin and weak bird. The breastbone is very easy to feel.</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: compromised bird</p> <p><u>Score 2 and 3</u>: reflect healthy birds with good muscle tone, feeling good coverage of flesh and muscle in the breast area.</p> <p>EoL hens will be less muscular than broilers or breeders due to their production cycle and genetics. End-of-lay hens may receive a body condition score of 1 and still be loaded.</p>	Yes
Muir et al. (2023)	Breast muscle score	<p><u>Score 0</u>: very lean breast muscle (cachectic)</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: slightly concave shape to the breast contour</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: ideally fleshed breast contour</p> <p><u>Score 3</u>: abundant (slightly excessive) breast muscle</p>	No

Table 17: Descriptions of emaciation or cachexia used to assess presence or absence of the condition.

Description reference	Original indicator name	Description	Specie
Avian Disease Manual (2013)	Emaciation	<p><u>Absence:</u> A nice growing bird will show a convex (rounded) contour of the breast with plump breast muscle and no protuberance of the keel.</p> <p><u>Presence:</u> marked concavity of the breast contour caused by a prominent keel with barely no pectoral muscles being felt.</p>	Poultry
Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Moe, et al. (2023)	Emaciation	<p><u>Presence:</u> prominent keel and marked muscle atrophy, little to no abdominal fat and gelatinous epicardial fat.</p>	Laying hens
Ortín et al. (2017)	Cachexia / retarded growth	<p><u>Cachexia:</u> Absence of perivisceral fat and alteration in consistency of the remaining fat. Prominent bones, specially the keel bone (muscular mass loss). Small internal organs (i.e. liver and spleen). Normal size of the animal, and comb and wattles proportioned to the size of the animal.</p> <p><u>Retarded growth:</u> marked decline in size. Low muscle mass, but with low atrophy in relation to the size of the animal. Internal organs proportioned to the size of the animal. Body and beak pale, with poor feather cover, small comb and wattles.</p> <p><u>Healthy but lean carcass:</u> variable amount of fat, but normal appearance. Low muscle mass, but with low atrophy in relation to the size of the animal. Internal organs proportioned to the size of the animal.</p>	Poultry

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

Emaciated or cachexic birds have increased risk of DoA and is argued that will likely suffer more from feed deprivation associated with transport than fit, heavier birds (Jacobs et al., 2017; LEGMONI Project et al., 2024). Emaciated or cachexic birds should be considered unfit for transport.

Genetics have an impact in body condition score, meaning that the definition of what is “lean” or “thin” can differ depending on the genetics. Laying hens have been selected for productive traits over the years and not for muscle composition, resulting in a more exposed keel bone than broilers (Chew et al., 2021). Thus, broiler breeder hens are heavier than, for example, a brown laying hen, and differences can also be seen between breeds of laying hens. However, thin hens should not be confused with emaciated or cachexic hens. Small or slightly thin birds with enough muscle and fat cover would be considered fit for transport, though preventive measures may be necessary (e.g. adjustment of loading density or use of curtains). Extreme cases of emaciation or cachexia are hardly confused with thin animals, but definition and examples of scoring for intermediate cases in different breeds could be necessary. Only the Welfare Quality Network (2019) method differentiates between two genetics (brown vs white hens) in their visual material for the assessment.

Definitions presented in [Table 17](#) are pretty clear, but some of the characteristics can only be seen in the slaughter line (post-mortem), not on farm. For the on-farm assessment, methods presented in [Table 16](#) are more useful. Criteria for fitness for transport assessment should consider the worst score of the used method. Gregory and Robins (1998), Welfare Quality Network (2019) and LEGMONI Project et al. (2024) are the ones that show the most detailed description, so are considered to be better for the assessment of this indicator, alongside with the visual material that some of them provide.

“Runts” or small animals are a particular case. If they have enough muscle and fat cover, they would be considered fit for transport. However, they will probably be condemned at the slaughter line, and can have problems when going through the waterbath (i.e. their heads could not reach the water), thus failing in becoming unconscious before bleeding. This is why runts should be identified either on farm or on lairage and processed separately, even if they are not emaciated.

Gaps of knowledge:

- Even if the methods for assessment are enough to identify extreme cases of emaciation and cachexia, fitness for transport assessment can be difficult in intermediate situations (thin but not emaciated animals).
- Scoring examples for different genetics are needed both to see examples of extreme cases and intermediate situations.
- The existing methods for assessment rely on palpation or visual inspection of the breast muscles, meaning that handling of the animals is expected. This can be time consuming, so an assessment strategy should be discussed.

11.7 Dehydration

Description of the indicator:

As said in [section 7](#), birds are water deprived during transport (seldom before catching), practice which can lead to prolonged thirst and dehydration. As defined by EFSA et al. (2022), prolonged thirst means that the bird has been unable to get enough water to satisfy its needs and experiences craving or urgent need for water, accompanied by an uneasy sensation (a negative affective state), and eventually leading to dehydration as metabolic requirements are not met. Dehydration is a condition of body water depletion (EFSA, 2011, defined for humans). Water can be lost from urine, faeces, the skin and respiratory tract (vapor) (Collett, 2012). Additionally, laying hens lose water when producing their eggs (Spada et al., 2012). When dehydrated, mechanisms of thirst stimulation are activated and the urge to drink increases in intensity until water intake returns body water to normal (Collett, 2012).

In domestic poultry, dehydration often causes visceral urate depositions (Pollock, 2006) and may exacerbate underlying health conditions like reduced blood volume and circulation, metabolic acidosis, arrhythmias, circulatory failure, increased susceptibility to heat stress, damage to the nervous system and toxemia) (Baker-Cook et al., 2021; Wurtz et al., 2024). It can also cause

pathologic states such as nephrosis, visceral gout, proventriculitis, cyanosis of the comb, and increases the likelihood of bacterial infections, which all will be indirectly contributing to increase mortality (Baker-Cook et al., 2021). Water deprivation itself is a stressor and has an additive effect intensifying the eventual health condition and increases suffering and response to the stressor (Baker-Cook et al., 2021).

Various factors can exacerbate the impact of water deprivation and modify an individual's response, such as environmental conditions, species, genetic line, and thus the productivity of laying hens: as eggs have a high water content, high-yielding hens may be more sensitive to water deprivation (Wurtz et al., 2024).

On farm dehydration is due to reduced water consumption that can be caused by the inability to reach water, an inadequate amount of water provided to the flock (i.e. by forced moulting or a problem with the drinking system), or other factors such as illness, injury, or social stress (Butterworth & Weeks, 2010; Rexhepi et al., 2015; Savory, 2010).

Water (and feed) deprivation prior to transport is a standard practice, which duration will depend on the on-farm and transport conditions. For this reason, assessing FFT in regards to dehydration is paramount as dehydrated birds prior to transport will suffer water deprivation during transport and until slaughter. Indeed, as highlighted by the Consortium of the Animal Transport Guides Project (2017), dehydration can be a major cause of transport morbidity and mortality especially in EoL hens on long distance travels.

Description of the method:

Dehydration may be detected by physiological indicators (for example, plasma osmolality, plasma chloride...). However, as highlighted by Wurtz et al. (2024), the relationship between the degree of dehydration and the degree of thirst is not clear, and physiological indicators for long term dehydration are not available. Moreover, as physiological indicators imply handling and sampling blood from each bird, they are not applicable to assess FFT of an entire flock.

Motivation tests have also been used as indicators of dehydration in various studies. For example, measure of voluntary water uptake from an open drinker was shown to be a valid measure of thirst in broiler chickens, as it increased proportionally with the duration of water deprivation (Sprenger et al., 2009). However, as highlighted by Vanderhasselt et al. (2013), such tests are quite time consuming and give no information about the individual's level of thirst (Sprenger et al., 2009). Therefore, it doesn't seem they could be used to assess an individual's FFT.

Animal based measures indicating dehydration such as skin turgor, colour of the comb or capillary refill time are debated and at this time it seems there is no clear protocol to be used, as their sensitivity is currently poor (Vanderhasselt et al., 2013).

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

Clearly, no severely dehydrated hen should be transported, as water deprivation until slaughter will only increase the negative welfare consequence for the bird. However, no indicator can be

used in practical conditions for the assessment of dehydration in the FFT context. EFSA et al. (2022) concluded that EoL hens subjected to water deprivation periods longer than 6 hours will experience prolonged thirst (the same as in broilers, but with an increased risk because hens are still producing eggs), that will increase with time. The total time of water deprivation should not exceed 12 hours in the “safe thermal zone” (see [figure 1](#)).

Gaps of knowledge:

- No indicator can be used in practical conditions for the assessment dehydration in the FFT context. Monitoring of total amount of water withdrawal time is the only recommendation currently set to minimize the risk of prolonged thirst, although it does not take into account the initial state of the animal.

11.8 Evident signs of illness

“Evident signs of illness” is not a single indicator but a set of indicators, and it should include all the obvious clinical signs of illness. As it is not possible to list all the possible situations occurring on farm, veterinary advise should be seek if an unusual sign of illness is encountered. For the present document, the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has decided to review the following categories that encompass the different indicators described in literature:

- Signs of respiratory disease: including distressed breathing and discharge from the eyes or nostrils
- Diarrhoea
- Signs of general infection: including abnormal colouring of the skin (dark red or very pale), other physical defects.
- Ascites (dilated abdomen/oedema)
- Neurological symptoms: including hunched posture or crouched posture.
- Moribund animal: including weak or clearly fatigued, not alert, swollen head or neck, abnormal colouring of the comb or wattles (dark red, purple or black).

Each of these categories will be described separately in order to facilitate comprehension, and then criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport and gaps of knowledge will be addressed together to facilitate discussion.

Signs of respiratory disease

Description of the indicator:

Respiratory disease consists in abnormal anatomy or function of the upper and/or lower respiratory tract and include infectious and non-infectious diseases (Taggers & Baron, 2023). Respiratory diseases are multifactorial problems in poultry, with viral and bacterial respiratory pathogens often concurrently present and most probably influencing one another (Umar et al., 2018). Respiratory infections are more common in birds than mammals as a consequence of the

structure of their respiratory tract (Samour, 2016) and can affect air passages, lungs or air sacs (Butcher et al., 2022).

Description of the method:

Various clinical symptoms can be observed directly on live animals and indicate signs of respiratory diseases, listed in [Table 18](#). Other signs that are also described in literature but without definition are the following:

- Cyanosis of comb and/or wattles (Butcher et al., 2022; He et al., 2022)
- Abnormal vocalizations (He et al., 2022; Samour, 2015)
- Occlusion of the nares (Doneley, 2016)
- Swollen wattles and sinuses, mucous discharge from mouth (Umar et al., 2018)

In some cases signs on individuals can not be easily seen but the whole flock can be diagnosed, for example, if sneezing is heard but not seen.

Table 18: Descriptions of respiratory signs used to assess presence or absence of the pathologic condition.

Description reference	Sign	Description
(Welfare Quality Network, 2019)	Eye pathologies	Swelling of the eyelids and the skin around the eyes, closure of the eye/eyes and discharge from the eyes
(Baker et al., 2020; Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021)	laboured breath, dyspnoea, shortness of breath, or gasping	Dyspnoea or laboured breathing happens when there is decreased oxygen perfusion to tissue and there is increased reparatory effort. It's linked to the sensation of shortness of breath. Breathing becomes difficult, uncomfortable, or labored i.e. by evidence of increased effort to breathe. Gasping is defined as deep breaths with open mouth and out of sync with normal breathing rhythm.
Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary (2021)	Exophthalmos	Abnormal protrusion of the eyeball or eyeballs.
(<i>Manual Merck de Veterinaria</i> , 2008)	Oculonasal discharge	Excretion of fluids from one or both nostrils or one or both eyes.
(Shankar, 2008)	Pump handle respiration	Birds extend their head and neck to facilitate breathing
(Butcher et al., 2022; Samour, 2015; Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021; Swayne, 2020)	Rales, rattles, respiratory gurgles	Abnormal breathing sound, adventitious sound besides the breathing sound. They may be heard in birds with infection of the lower respiratory tract.
(Setzen & Platt, 2019; Songu & Cingi, 2009)	Sneezing*	Coordinated protective respiratory reflex which occurs due to stimulation of the upper respiratory tract, particularly the nasal cavity. It is considered as a reflex to evacuate irritants from the nasal cavities.

* The sneezing reflex exists in animals for which the smell sensation is vital to survive and can be used to clean the nasal cavity (Songu & Cingi, 2009), so that is why sneezing is a key clinical sign to detect when there are respiratory diseases in poultry (Carpentier et al., 2019). Sometimes sneezing is described alongside with "coughing". Although the physiology and function of coughing in birds is similar to mammals, it involves a different mechanism. Unlike mammals, where the diaphragm serves as the primary muscle for inhalation, birds utilize a unique system of air sacs and a rigid

lung structure to facilitate respiration. Hence, birds rely on muscles surrounding the air sacs and trachea to breathe and cough. This anatomic difference suggests that coughing has a limited effect in birds (as for clearing the lower respiratory tract) compared to mammals (Wang et al., 2019).

Diarrhoea

Description of the indicator:

Diarrhoea is an increase in the volume, wateriness, or frequency of bowel movements (*Manual Merck de Veterinaria*, 2008), which in poultry is usually seen as freshly soiled plumage beneath the tail (EFSA et al., 2022). In general, the causes are either of nutritional or infectious origin (Pattison, 1987). In poultry production, urine and faeces are excreted simultaneously through the cloaca, making it difficult to distinguish polyuria from diarrhoea, so it can also be referred to as “flushing” (increased liquid water excretion rate) (Collett, 2012).

Description of the method:

The available methods are described as presence or absence of the pathologic condition ([Table 19](#)).

Table 19: Methods for assessing diarrhoea on farm described for laying hens or chickens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Zhang et al. (2017)	Diarrhoea	Absence: shaped faeces, soft and easy to cut. Presence: faeces falling out of shape, liquid.	No
Welfare Quality Network (2019)	Enteritis	Presence: Enteritis includes gut infections or digestive metabolism abnormalities often resulting in altered faecal state – discoloured faeces or increased liquid content or diarrhoea. Scoring is based on whether soiled feathers or skin are visible.	No
Marchewka et al. (2020)	Diarrhoea	Presence: Altered fecal state—discolored feces or increased liquid content	No
Goransson et al. (2023)	Diarrhoea	Presence: altered faecal state with increased liquid content	No

Signs of general infection

Description of the indicator:

An infectious process is a clinical term that indicates the invasion or contamination of a host caused by a pathogen (fungi, bacteria, protozoa, viruses or prions), their products (toxins) or both at the same time. Involves an immune response and structural damage and tissue injury to the host. Causes of a general infectious process can be diverse, but it evolves in a generalized way, with a systemic affection (Ortín et al., 2017).

Description of the method:

Main signs of a general infection are:

- Swollen head or neck (swollen, puffy heads and sinuses)
- Abnormal colouring of the skin (dark red or very pale)

- Abnormal colouring of the comb or wattles (dark red, purple or black)

These signs are non-specific and have also been associated with moribund animals (EFSA et al., 2022). For example, abnormal colouring of the skin can be associated with cardiac abnormalities, respiratory problems, fever, anemia, or Marek's disease (Canada Health of Animals Legislation, 2024; Mogrovejo Vera, 2021).

Ascites

Description of the indicator:

Ascites is a pathologic state of multifactorial aetiology which manifests as an accumulation of fluid in the abdominal cavity (Balog et al., 2000; Ortín et al., 2017). The primary stimulus of ascites syndrome is believed to be hypoxia, when the demand for oxygen exceeds its cardiopulmonary capacity, precipitating heart failure, ascites syndrome and ultimately death (Balog et al., 2000; Balog et al., 2003; Leeson, 2007). It is a common condemnation cause at slaughterhouse both in broilers and layers (Gretarsson, Kittelsen, Oppermann Moe, et al., 2023; Saraiva et al., 2021) occurring more frequently in older hens (Saraiva, 2019). A similar condition that could be mistaken for ascites is "egg bound". A hard, solid abdomen can denote egg bound and a soft abdomen can denote ascites (Hen Central).

Description of the method:

Ascites is usually identified post-mortem at the slaughter line, where the following signs can be seen: fluid in the abdominal cavity, either clear or yellow, where part of it coagulates and forms a jelly-like mass that is deposited on the liver and other viscera (Ortín et al., 2017). Other characteristic symptoms of the disease process are enlarged, flaccid hearts and variable liver changes (congestion and mottling or a thickening of the capsule with an overall shrunken appearance)(Balog et al., 2000).

It's identification ante-mortem is difficult, and it depends on secondary clinical signs, as: distended abdomen, panting, comb and wattles cyanosis, atrophied comb, pale head, closed eyes, open mouth, lethargy, raised plumage (Ortín et al., 2017).

Neurological symptoms

Description of the indicator:

Aviary birds frequently develop clinical signs associated with the central or peripheral nervous system (Samour, 2015). The neurological disease signs in birds are often nonspecific, consequently a disease diagnosis using external clinical signs alone is rarely achieved (Hunt, 2015). The symptoms that usually appear in poultry are: ataxia, tremor, paralysis, head twisting or twirling, torticollis (neck twisting), spasms, convulsions and hunched or crouched posture.

Depending on the region of the damage, the clinical signs will change. Brain damage may result in clinical signs such as prostration, tremors, head tilt, and star-gazing posture; peripheral nerve

damage may result in partial or complete paralysis; injury or disease may alter normal stance and locomotion; a chicken with unilateral leg paralysis due to sciatic nerve damage will sit with the paralyzed leg extended forward; a bird with a lumbar spine lesion due to spondylolisthesis (congenital) or vertebral osteomyelitis (infectious) may develop bilateral leg paralysis and will sit back on its hocks with both legs extended forward (Linares et al., 2018).

The most common diseases that cause the neurological problems in poultry are: Newcastle disease, Marek's disease, Avian encephalomyelitis virus, paratuberculosis and avian influenza.

Description of the method:

Various clinical neurological symptoms can be observed directly on live animals. Descriptions to these symptoms are listed in [Table 20](#), to assess their presence or absence.

Table 20: Descriptions of neurological symptoms used to assess presence or absence of the pathologic condition.

Description reference	Sign	Description
(Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021)	Ataxia	Failure of muscular coordination; irregularity of muscular action.
(Louis & Bain, 2022) (Smaga, 2003)	Tremor	Involuntary, rhythmic, oscillatory movement of a body part.
(Stone & Aybek, 2016)	Paralysis	Complete or partial loss of motor function of the muscles of the posterior limb or of cervical musculature or the whole body.
(Collins et al., 2011)	Head twisting/twirling	Abnormal head movements and orientation.
(Collins et al., 2011)	Circling	Movement that refers to walking in circles
(Farrow, 2006)	Torticollis	sustained, abnormal twisting of the neck, typically to one side or the other, caused by asymmetric tension in the cervical musculature.
(Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021)	Spasm	Persistent, involuntary contraction of a muscle or muscle groups
(Saunders comprehensive veterinary dictionary, 2021)	Convulsions	Involuntary violent contraction of voluntary muscles that causes irregular movements, in some muscle groups or generalized throughout the body
(EFSA et al., 2022) (Butterworth & Weeks, 2010)	Hunched posture	Neck is retracted down towards the body, the tail may droop, the general appearance is more rounded and contracted and the eyes are often closed

Moribund animal

Description of the indicator:

A moribund animal is an animal in the state of dying or at the point of death (Stokes, 2002), without prospect of recovery. Moribund animals can appear weak or clearly fatigued, not alert, or present other indicators or diseases (e.g. dehydration, neurological signs, etc).

Description of the method:

There are several clinical signs indicative of a moribund condition, as: impaired ambulation (unable to or struggling to move when approached), excessive weight loss and extreme emaciation, lack of physical or mental alertness, laboured breathing, prolonged inability to remain upright (Stokes, 2002), described for laboratory animals), swollen head or neck, abnormal colouring of the comb or wattles (dark red, purple or black) (EFSA et al., 2022).

General discussion for evident signs of illness

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

Weak and ill animals will be at high risk of pain and compromised welfare during transport. When a flock presents general signs of illness (i.e. high levels of mortality), it has been correlated to DoA or other physiological indices after transport in both broilers and EoL hens (EFSA et al., 2022). Thus, if an animal presents evident signs of illness, it should be considered unfit for transport. When a flock is diagnosed with a disease by a veterinarian or laboratory, it shall be discussed if transportation to the slaughterhouse could be avoided depending on the diagnosis.

However, *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005* states that “sick or injured animals may be considered fit for transport if they are: slightly injured or ill and transport would not cause additional suffering; in cases of doubt, veterinary advice shall be sought”. This complicates the assessment of illness, as “severity” and “additional suffering” have to be taken into account.

The indicators described above are either present or absent, without scoring scales, and sometimes overlapped (e.g. as discussed for moribund signs). Most of them are referred in literature as evident signs of illness, so their sole presence would mean that the animal is unfit for transport. Nevertheless, some poultry guidelines (*Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual*, 2019) considers that the following signs require further assessment:

- Diarrhoea: as it can be due to diet or illness, the state of the flock should be checked. However, they state that if an individual bird with diarrhoea also shows any other symptom of illness, it should be considered unfit for transport.
- Sneezing: as they can be present as a flock problem and not only as an individual’s issue, further assessment of the flock is recommended.

Gaps of knowledge:

- There are a lot of signs of illness that should be taken into account. In some cases a clear definition for laying hens is missing, as the terms are usually generically described. Photographic references are mostly not presented in literature.
- Signs that can be seen in the whole flock (i.e. diarrhoea or respiratory signs) should be further assessed before a decision about FFT can be made.
- Legislation states that “slightly ill” animals can be fit for transport. As the indicators presented above are either present or absent, it is unclear whether the sole presence of any of the cited

indicators would mean that the animal is unfit, or if some of the indicators would mean a less “severe” situation.

11.9 Poor feather cover (in low effective temperature)

Description of the indicator:

The plumage condition of laying hens is regarded as an indicator of animal health, behaviour and welfare (LayWel Project et al., 2006; Welfare Quality Network, 2019). Feathers are integument features unique to birds. They are typically smooth, flexible and largely composed of beta-keratin protein. The various feather types distributed over the body enable birds to carry out locomotive, reproductive and social behaviours; comfort behaviours as preening, feather raising and dustbathing; as well as thermoregulatory behaviours, as feathers permit birds to stay warm and dry by providing insulation and a waterproof exterior (C Decina et al., 2019) (EFSA et al., 2022). Birds conserve body heat with specially constructed down feathers, the structure of which helps to trap the warm air in the plumage enabling thermal insulation properties (*Poultry feather and skin: The poultry integument in health and welfare*, 2019).

Feather cover of laying hens declines as the bird ages. In fact, laying hens usually reach the end of the laying period with poor feather cover (Glatz, 2001). Poor feather coverage includes both feather damage and feather loss. Feather damage is described as a phenomenon in which feathers are broken, deformed or deviated from a smooth and intact state (C Decina et al., 2019), whereas feather loss implies the shedding of the feathers revealing the underlying down feathers and/or bare patches of skin (C Decina et al., 2019).

A non-intact feather cover can be a multifactorial problem with potentially different underlying causes and associated risk factors (Caitlin Decina et al., 2019). This condition may be caused by natural processes, such as moulting; abrasion due to housing equipment, such as feeding tracks; deficiencies in feed composition; or as a result of injurious pecking by other birds (damaging bird-to-bird pecking whereby pecks to the feathers or tissue of another bird causing plumage or tissue damage or skin wounds) (Campe et al., 2018; EFSA et al., 2022; Mullan et al., 2016).

The location of the feather damage or loss on the bird can help to provide an indication of potential cause of the impairment (Hennovation, Temple, van Niekerk, et al., 2017; Main et al., 2012). For instance, poor feather coverage at the neck, back/rump and the tail usually indicate severe feather pecking (re-directed foraging, comfort and exploratory behaviours), which should not be confused with aggressive pecking (motivated by resource defence or hierarchy formation). Aggressive pecking is usually directed to the head region (Welfare Quality Network, 2019). Damage to the feathers of the neck can be caused by abrasions at the feeding trough whereas feather loss to the belly region can be seen in highly productive animals. However, the latter can also be caused by vent pecking (Campe et al., 2018; C Decina et al., 2019; Welfare Quality Network, 2019).

Feather loss and feather damage undoubtedly cause bird discomfort and present a significant welfare issue, especially when hens are exposed to low effective temperatures (C Decina et al., 2019; EFSA et al., 2022). Poor feather cover reduces the capacity for thermal insulation from feathers (Zhu et al., 2021) making birds more sensitive to cold and/or wet weather. Apart from being poorly feathered, EoL hens are metabolically exhausted and have minimal body fat and muscle at the end of the egg laying production cycle, making them less efficient to keep their body temperature by shivering (EFSA et al., 2022).

As explained in [section 7](#), cold stress is a welfare concern for EoL hens who are poorly feathered and transported in low temperatures.

Description of the method:

Two main methods are commonly used to assess feather cover. The first is a visual evaluation, either of the whole body or of specific body regions. The second involves using technology, like infrared thermography, which has been shown to effectively assess feather condition in laying hens (Raine et al., 2020). However, the required infrared thermography equipment currently makes this method potentially challenging for the assessment of FFT during official inspections.

The available visual methods for feather cover assessment are detailed in [Table 21](#). All of them use classifications per body part, but the number of body parts assessed varies. The methods can be used both for comparison of scores for individual body parts or for the whole body (using the worst score encountered). Some of them require the handling of the hen, but some of them have been developed to avoid handling and are also correlated with the assessment of handled birds (EFSA et al., 2023).

Table 21: Methods for assessing feather cover on farm described for laying hens.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
(Bilcík & Keeling, 1999)	Feather condition*	<p><u>11 regions</u>: head, upper neck (back side of the neck), back (part between wings), rump, tail, belly (abdomen), breast, under neck (front side of the neck), wings-primary feathers, wings-coverts and legs.</p> <p>Scoring body</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: intact feathers</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: some feathers scruffy, up to 3 missing feathers</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: more damaged feathers, >3 feathers missing</p> <p><u>Score 3</u>: Bald patch <5 cm diameter or <50% of area</p> <p><u>Score 4</u>: Bald patch >5 cm diameter or >50% of area</p> <p><u>Score 5</u>: completely denuded area</p> <p>Scoring Flight feathers</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: intact feathers</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: few feather separated but none broken or missing</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: a lot of feathers separated and/or a few broken or missing</p>	No

		<p><u>Score 3</u>: all feathers separated, a lot of broken or missing feathers</p> <p><u>Score 4</u>: most of the feathers missing or broken</p> <p><u>Score 5</u>: almost all feathers missing</p>	
(LayWel Project et al., 2006; Tauson et al., 2005)	Plumage condition*	<p><u>6 regions</u>: neck, breast, cloaca/vent, back, wings and tail. <u>Scores of 1-4</u> with photographic references, but no description. The higher the score, the better the status of the integument.</p> <p>The system can be used both for comparison of scores for individual body parts (scores 1, 2, 3 or 4) or pooled for the whole body (i.e. scores 6, 7, etc. up to 24).</p>	Yes
(Kjaer et al., 2011), reduced version of the LayWel system	Plumage condition*	<p><u>4 regions</u> (neck, back, wings and tail)</p> <p>Scoring birds on the ground without catching and handling birds at all. Same scoring references than LayWel system.</p>	Yes
AssureWel (Main et al., 2012)	Feather cover	<p><u>2 regions</u>: head and neck area, and the back and rump area of the bird. Score separately for the head and neck area, and the back and rump area.</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: no/minimal feather loss. No bare skin visible, no or slight wear, only single feathers missing.</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: slight feather loss. Moderate wear, damaged feathers or 2 or more adjacent feathers missing up to bare skin visible < 5 cm maximum dimension.</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: moderate/severe feather loss. Bare skin visible \geq 5 cm maximum dimension</p>	No
(Welfare Quality Network, 2019)	Plumage damage*	<p><u>3 regions</u>: neck, back/rump and belly.</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: no or slight wear, (nearly) complete feathering (only single feathers lacking).</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: moderate wear, i.e. damaged feathers (worn, deformed) or one or more featherless areas < 5 cm in diameter at the largest extent.</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: at least one featherless area \geq 5 cm in diameter at the largest extent.</p>	Yes, but only during training courses
(Beaulac et al., 2020) (adapted from the study by (Davami et al., 1987) and (Sarica et al., 2008)	Feather condition	<p><u>4 regions</u>: neck, back, breast, and wings.</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: no feather cover</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: greater than 50% of the plumage is missing</p> <p><u>Score 3</u>: less than 50% of the plumage is missing</p> <p><u>Score 4</u>: full intact plumage</p>	No
Transect method (Vasdal et al., 2022)	Feather loss	<p><u>4 regions</u>: head, neck, back and vent.</p> <p><u>Score 0</u>: no loss</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: <5 cm</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: >5cm</p>	No
(Özentürk et al., 2023)	Feather loss	<p><u>6 regions</u>: neck, breast, back, wing, tail, and cloaca.</p> <p><u>Score 1</u>: >75% of the feathers of the body region missing.</p> <p><u>Score 2</u>: >50% and <75% of the feathers of the body region missing.</p> <p><u>Score 3</u>: >25% and <50% of the feathers of the body region missing.</p> <p><u>Score 4</u>: no feather loss or <25% of the feathers of the body region missing.</p>	No

*It can also be carried out post-mortem but pre-scald (EFSA et al., 2023).

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

In the *Council Regulation (EC) 1/2005* it is specified that “No animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey, and all animals shall be transported in conditions guaranteed not to cause them injury or unnecessary suffering”. When transporting EoL hens, particularly in cold

weather, the condition of their feather cover is a critical factor in determining their fitness for transport. EFSA et al. (2022) specifies that EoL hens with poor feather cover are unfit for travel if transported in cold conditions without appropriate preventive and corrective measures to address cold stress. Feather cover is a strong predictor of mortality risk during transit; well-feathered birds are more likely to survive the journey, while those with inadequate feather cover face a significantly higher risk of cold stress and potential mortality (Weeks et al., 2012).

EoL hens are particularly vulnerable due to their generally poorer feather cover and limited metabolic reserves. Consequently, the lower limit for safe transport temperatures for these hens is higher than for other poultry. Furthermore, birds may be exposed to both wind and wetting at all stages of transport both of which have a profound chilling effect mimicking lower temperatures, and conditions of the vehicle (i.e. curtains, location within the vehicle) are also affecting the animals. (EFSA et al., 2022) states that as it might be difficult to recommend different limits upon feathering of EoL hens, a critical temperature threshold of 18°C is recommended, regardless of feather cover. If the temperature drops below this level, the hens' ability to cope with cold stress diminishes considerably, increasing the likelihood of cold stress during transport. Therefore, maintaining a temperature above this threshold within transport containers is crucial to prevent cold stress. If this cannot be guaranteed, feather coverage should be taken into account. For instance, under low-temperature conditions, a hen with severe feather loss is at a heightened risk of suffering and mortality, thereby making it unfit for transport. In contrast, a hen with only partial feather loss, such as on the breast, might still be considered fit for transport from an animal welfare perspective under the same environmental conditions. Consideration on the relationship between the feather cover and the vehicle's ventilation and the position of the animals within the vehicle is also important. Hens with poor feather cover are at a significantly higher risk of cold stress when placed in positions within the vehicle that are exposed to greater ventilation or are located at the rear and outer parts of the vehicle during low-temperature conditions (EFSA et al., 2022).

Assessing feather cover in EoL hens and monitoring temperature prior to transport is essential. Visual inspection of the flock without catching the birds can reveal major problems in plumage coverage, that will be relevant if the animals should be transported in low temperatures. Methods that evaluate regions of the body most susceptible to heat loss, such as the back and breast, without catching the birds, could be particularly useful. As heat exit points, the absence of feathers on the neck region, tail and rump is of minor importance for the suitability of transport. However, feather damage to the back and breast region may cause severe heat losses and excessive energy intake due to poor insulation (Tauson et al., 2005).

Gaps of knowledge:

- Although multiple scoring methods for assessing feather cover in relation to animal welfare have been validated for laying hens on farms, there is no scoring method for assessing feather cover in terms of FFT.

- Methods that evaluate regions of the body most susceptible to heat loss, such as the back and breast, without catching the birds, could be particularly useful. However, thresholds regarding FFT should be provided.
- EFSA et al. (2022) recommends a critical temperature threshold of 18°C, regardless of the feather coverage. However, if hens should be transported in lower temperatures, then feather coverage of the flock, characteristics of the vehicle and other preventive measures should be taken into consideration. There is actually lack of guidance about how to proceed in this situation.

11.10 Wet plumage (in low effective temperature)

Description of the indicator:

As said before, EoL hens are highly vulnerable to cold stress during transportation due to poor feather coverage and metabolic exhaustion. This lack of insulation and energy reserves makes them sensitive to low temperatures and prone to higher mortality rates, especially during colder months (FAWC, 2019). Exposure to wind and wetting during transport further reduces the insulating capacity of their plumage, increasing the risk of hypothermia and stress (Knezacek et al., 2010). EoL hens are particularly at risk of hypothermia when located on the periphery of transport containers (FAWC, 2019).

Wetting and air movement have a significant impact on insulation, leading to hypothermia in mild temperatures that would only represent a small decrease in body temperature if birds had been kept dry (EFSA et al., 2022). The risk of wetting from sources such as rain, snow, melted ice, road spray at air inlets and wetting during catching and loading should be considered. Wetting could also come from liquid faeces. Loading into wet containers in cold weather may cause initial chilling of the animals. During transport in cold and humid conditions, lack of curtains to protect the birds and absence of a heating system in the vehicle can rapidly decrease the perceived temperature. The combined effects of disrupted feather insulation from wetting, enhanced convective cooling by air movement, and increased evaporative cooling from the wetted surface significantly increase the risk of cold stress, especially in lower air temperatures (EFSA et al., 2022).

Description of the method:

Currently, there is no protocol to evaluate the indicator "Wet plumage " in EoL hens. However, there are some welfare protocols for assessing the indicator "wet animals" in other species such as quails and rabbits. The method used in quails is shown in [Table 22](#).

Table 22: Method for assessing wet birds on farm described for quails.

Assessment method reference	Original indicator name	Scoring scale and definitions	Visual material
Welfare (2023a)	Wet animals	Score 0: the animal has all its feathers dry. Score 2: there is any part of its body wet.	Yes, but only during training courses

Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport:

According to EFSA et al. (2022), EoL hens with poor feather cover are unfit to travel if they are to be transported in cold weather without the application of preventive and corrective measures during transport. The same criterion should be considered for wet animals under similar conditions. *Alberta poultry handling and transportation manual* (2019) state that wet birds should not be transported; they should first be allowed to dry, or measures are taken to ensure proper thermal comfort during transport.

Other preventive measures could be also taken into account to prevent cold stress: as it has been said before, maintain an internal temperature of at least 18°C is recommended; the vehicle characteristics should be taken into account (use of curtains or solid panels, proper ventilation without excessive air velocity); any wetting of crates and drawers and exposure to rain should also be avoided (EFSA et al., 2022).

Gaps of knowledge:

- There is a need to validate a method for scoring wet plumage in EoL hens, although the method for assessing individual wet animals could be easily adapted from the one described in quails.
- There is a lack of information about how to handle wet animals. For instance, if only few wet animals are encountered, they could still be fit for transport if preventive measures are taken. However, if most hens have visibly wet or soaked plumage, transport conditions should be reconsidered to determine if the entire flock is fit for transport.

12 Conclusions

Assessing the fitness of the end-of-lay hens to withstand the journey are essential to ensure an adequate level of welfare during transportation. However, a substantial quantity of gaps of knowledge have been found during the review of the indicators to assess fitness for transport. Definitions and descriptions of the indicators are essential as a first step in the fitness assessment but valid and specific definitions are missing in some cases (e.g. severe open wounds, severe lameness, some of the terms for evident signs of illness). Scoring methods validated for laying hens on farm do not always exist, and even if they do, there is no specific scoring methods for assessing them in terms of FFT (e.g. severe open wounds, broken bones and dislocations, keel bone damage, dehydration, poor feather cover, wet plumage). Even if assessment methods are available, sometimes a threshold is missing to differentiate whether the animals are fit or unfit for the transport (e.g. severe open wounds, severe lameness, toe damage, keel bone damage, evident signs of illness, poor feather cover). Lastly, some of the existing methods for the assessment rely on palpation or visual inspection, meaning that handling of the animals is expected. This can be time consuming, and an assessment strategy should be discussed.

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA plans to work further in this topic in order to produce practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of end-of-lay hens (period 2025-2027) in order to deliver tools immediately usable by official inspectors assessing animal welfare. Criteria for the assessment of fitness for transport should be discussed further and the gaps of knowledge encountered should be addressed before practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of end-of-lay hens can be produced. Scoring audio visual examples are also needed for all the indicators in order to develop practical guidelines to assess fitness for transport of end-of-lay hens.

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About EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is one of the four European Union Reference Centres for Animal Welfare. It focuses on poultry and other small farmed animals welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from hatch/birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's main objective is to scientifically and technically support the European Commission and Member States for implementation of welfare legislation. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens;
- Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

Partners

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following four partner institutions:

- ANSES, France
- IRTA, Spain
- ANIVET, AU, Denmark
- IZSLER, Italy

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Activities of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Good Practices
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics, identify research needs and perform scientific and technical studies to fill the gaps of knowledge;
- Training
Reviewing existing training activities and developing new training materials, webinars and knowledge pills for official inspectors and competent authorities;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, and newsletter.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of poultry and other small farmed animals' welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of poultry and other small farmed animals welfare in the EU. For more information go to the Q2E webform available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw>. All Q2E answers are available [online](#).